

Land Based Pump Ashore IMTA System

PRODUCTION MANUAL

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IMTA: Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture

1. ASTRAL PRODUCTION MANUAL - LAND BASED PUMP ASHORE IMTA SYSTEM

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertiliser and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders such as bivalves, urchins, sea cucumber) enhance growth in this type of system. IMTA systems can be open water or land-based, marine or freshwater, with a variety of different species at differing trophic levels. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering costs, providing product diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability¹.

This manual contains detailed descriptions of the methods employed to produce the ASTRAL species trialled in land-based pump ashore systems. This manual will give guidance on how to grow the species and the parameters needed for their successful production, including welfare, health and biosecurity. The ASTRAL land-based pump ashore species included fed and extractive species of abalone, sea urchins and seaweed.

¹ Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

2. SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON IMTA PRODUCTION AND IMTA RESEARCH PROJECTS

ASTRAL H2020 project

<https://www.astral-project.eu/>

IMPAQT H2020 project

<https://impaqtproject.eu/about-impaqt/>

IMPAQT massive open online course (MOOC) in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Precision Aquaculture

<https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=7116>

AquaVitae H2020 project

<https://aquavitaeproject.eu/>

AquaVitae MOOC - Sustainable Aquaculture for Low Trophic Species

<https://open.uit.no/courses/course-v1:UiT+SALTS101+AquaVitae/about>

INTEGRATE project (INTERREG Atlantic Area 2014-2020 Programme) – Transition towards IMTA in the Atlantic Area

<https://integrate-imta.eu/>

IDREEM EU FP7 project – Increasing Industrial Resource Efficiency in European Mariculture

<https://www.bmrs.ie/bmrs-projects/past/idreem>

The Benefits of IMTA

IMTA benefits are environmental sustainability through bio-mitigation, economic stability through product diversification and, risk reduction and social acceptability through better management practices. IMTA may lead to increased biomass production, waste reduction, and new opportunities with regard to spatial use and species diversification.

The following are the benefits IMTA can potentially bring to a predominantly monoculture activity:

- Reduction in ecological impacts.
- Shift from a linear to a more circular model, allowing for a whole ecosystem approach.
- “Waste” reduction service to the industry through bioremediation. The “wastes” become “co-products”, using the vocabulary of circular economy.
- Additional crops produced in IMTA (e.g., seaweeds) can be used as feed or feed ingredients for fed species, enhancing circularity and reducing feed costs.
- Inclusion of seaweeds in IMTA allows for increased recirculation and a reduction in pumping (electrical) costs.
- Full recirculation in IMTA can provide protection to farms during harmful algal blooms (HABs) as well as other adverse environmental events (by not pumping seawater from the adjacent ocean during adverse environmental/HAB events).
- Seaweeds in IMTA systems or as a feed/aquafeed ingredients have a beneficial impact on the microbiome.
- IMTA improves the societal perception of aquaculture.
- IMTA grown products may have a market advantage.
- Different IMTA models can bring different community benefits – such as with re-stocking initiatives.

- IMTA optimises the space that is available, allowing numerous products to be produced within the same space, utilising the resource effectively and efficiently.
- IMTA offers a commercial benefit from growing other products on the site.
- Diversity provides alternative incomes and cash-flows, increasing the resilience of the business.
- Beyond biomass – true value in added ecosystem services and nutrient trading credits that some low trophic species provide before being valued at the farm gate².

² Chopin, T., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Troell, M., Hurd, C.L., Costello, M.J., Backman, S., Buschmann, A., Cuhel, R., Duarte, C.M., Gröndahl, F., Heasman, K., Haroun, R.J., Johansen, J., Jueterbock, A., Lench, M., Lindell, S., Pavia, H., Ricart, A.M., Sundell, K.S., and Yarish, C., 2024. Deep-ocean seaweed dumping for carbon sequestration: questionable, risky and not the best use of valuable biomass. *One Earth* 7(3): 359–364.

The Challenges of IMTA

The challenges faced by IMTA production are largely economic and regulatory. Generally, there is an imbalance in income between the trophic layers and this can discourage the adoption of the concept. Adding other trophic levels to monoculture set-ups increases the complexity of farm husbandry and infrastructure, and increases costs and efforts. Farmers are familiar with current systems and change is often considered unattractive and can be risky.

Further research needs to be carried out to demonstrate that profits can increase compared to those of conventional production systems. Issues of awareness and education about these innovative production systems need to be addressed. Concerns around biosecurity when additional species are introduced, or when water is recirculated or co-products are returned to the systems as feed, need to be researched and assurance given to allow for increased societal acceptance of IMTA products.

Competition for space when low-trophic, lower value, species are introduced into systems can cause problems; however, the economic, biological and societal benefits of integration need to be demonstrated. The whole value of the IMTA production systems and the ecosystem services they provide have to first be recognised. This is the phase we are presently in. Next will be the valuation/monetisation of these services and their uses for regulatory and financial incentives to make aquaculturists, regulators, aquaculture practices and society evolve.

Production System

Land-based IMTA carried out in the ASTRAL project refers to species production in either recirculating inshore biofloc systems or land-based pump ashore systems with partial water recirculation, as in the case of IMTA lab South Africa. Recirculation of water enables more control of certain physical and chemical parameters in production systems, including temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and nutrients, with the level of independence from the ambient environment dependent on the extent of the recirculation and geographic location.

Location, Climate and Species

The land-based pump ashore IMTA production described in this manual has taken place at Buffeljags Abalone (<https://www.vikingaquaculture.co.za/abalone/farming/>), which is located on a pristine stretch of coastline near the remote settlement of Buffeljags on the Cape south coast (34°45'14.7" S 19°36'51.9" E) of South Africa (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of IMTA lab South Africa — Buffeljags Abalone Farm. ©B. Macey.

The Cape south coast has a temperate climate that is characterised by long warm and dry summers and cool and wet, but relatively short winters. The average annual air temperature in the region is 17 °C and is at its highest in January/February and lowest in July.

Over the course of the year, the air temperature typically varies from 8.8 °C to 24.5 °C and is rarely below 5 °C or above 29 °C³. All seawater to produce the species at IMTA lab South Africa is pumped directly from the Atlantic Ocean, via an intake pipe located amongst the kelp beds directly in front of the farm. The mean water temperatures for the Atlantic Ocean in this area are 15.6 °C, with an absolute minimum of 9 °C to an absolute maximum of 23.5 °C (20-year average). Salinity at this site is ca. 35 psu.

Table 1. Species cultivated at the South African IMTA lab.

COMMON NAME	LATIN NAME	ROLE IN IMTA
Abalone	<i>Haliotis midae</i>	Fed species
Sea lettuce	<i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	Extractive species
Collector sea urchin	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	Novel (fed) species
Cape sea urchin	<i>Parechinus angulosus</i>	Novel (fed) species

The species at the IMTA lab South Africa (Table 1, Figure 2) are categorised as: fed, extractive, or novel species:

1. Fed species: Feed is inputted to the system for the South African abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and the tropical sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*). As a result, the animals release waste/nutrients into the water that is used as a nutrient source for the extractive seaweed species grown in the integrated system.

³ <https://weatherspark.com/y/82961/Average-Weather-in-Cape-Town-South-Africa-Year-Round>

2. Extractive species: Dissolved nutrients are extracted by the seaweed *Ulva lacinulata* that is grown in D-ended paddle raceway systems adjacent to the abalone systems. The seaweed absorbs the dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), which allows for partial to full water recirculation, and *Ulva* grown in the system serves as a supplementary feed for the abalone and urchins.

3. Novel species: Tropical sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, are fed with seaweeds grown in the IMTA process enhancing circularity; and the temperate sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, are fed with seaweeds and their faecal material is used as supplementary feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone, *Haliotis midae*, improving abalone growth/health and enhancing circularity.

Figure 2. Species cultivated at IMTA lab South Africa. (A) South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, ©J. Bolton; (B) sea lettuce, *Ulva lacinulata*, ©M. Cyrus; (C) collector sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, ©B. de Vos; and (D) Cape sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*. ©M. Brink-Hull.

1. INTEGRATED ABALONE-ULVA SYSTEMS

Buffeljags Abalone Farm produces approximately 450 tonnes of the abalone *Haliotis midae* and 600 tonnes of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata* annually. The farm is one of the first large commercial abalone farms in South Africa to consistently recirculate 50 % of their seawater by making use of the bioremediation capacity of *Ulva*. To augment biosecurity, Buffeljags Abalone has been specifically designed to consist of modular units. There are seven modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems at the farm, referred to as platforms, which are each composed of four clusters that each consist of one D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway and 42 abalone raceway tanks (6 rows each made of 7 abalone raceway tanks) (Figure 3). All the effluent water leaving the abalone tanks is bioremediated by *Ulva* in the adjacent paddle-raceway before being mixed with 50 % fresh seawater in the sump. The sump is also equipped with a protein skimmer to remove further waste and dissolved organic nutrients from the bioremediated seawater before it is returned to the abalone raceways. The clusters do not share water, equipment and other fomites, and various biosecurity measures are implemented to minimise the risk(s) of introducing an infectious disease and spreading it to the animals at a facility and/or between clusters.

Figure 3. Land-based pump ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacunculata*) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. (A) Aerial photograph of the modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA, ©Viking Aquaculture. (B) Schematic of the IMTA process in a single abalone-*Ulva* cluster. ©B. Macey.

Abalone are cultivated in baskets ($L \times W \times D$: $0.8 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$ m), generally made of 6 mm oyster mesh or perforated PVC (Figure 4), that are suspended in the fiberglass abalone raceway tanks ($L \times W \times D$: $6 \times 1.8 \times 0.8$ m). Each tank has a volume of ca. 8.5 m^3 and can accommodate up to 20 baskets, which are each fitted with PVC dividers (Figure 4d) to increase the surface area within each basket for abalone to attach. The dividers (vertical plates) are typically covered with a feeding plate (Figure 4e) where formulated feed is placed. Seaweed, such as kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) or *Ulva*, are placed under the feeding plate. Influent water enters on one side of the raceway tank and effluent water exits the opposite side of the tank through a standpipe (Figure 4). Typical flow rates in abalone raceways systems are between $5 - 9 \text{ L s}^{-1} \text{ t}^{-1}$ of abalone⁴. In general, the total volume in an abalone raceway is replaced once every 2 hours. Water movement and aeration within the raceways is facilitated by air-diffusers that are positioned horizontally under the baskets at the base of the fiberglass raceways. Air to these diffusers is provided by large blowers.

Figure 4. Schematic (side view) of a typical abalone raceway tank used on most South African abalone farms. Adapted from ©Yearsley, 2008. (a) Influent water enters raceway tank; (b) effluent water leaves through standpipe; (c) oyster mesh/perforated PVC baskets holding abalone; (d) vertical plates in abalone baskets; (e) feeding plate covering abalone baskets; (f) perforated PVC pipe attached to bottom of tank for aeration.

The D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceways in each cluster have a volume of ca. 150 m^3 ($L \times W \times D$: $30 \times 10 \times 0.5$ m). The shallow paddle-raceways are generally constructed out of concrete and are lined with a white PVC liner to promote the reflection of sunlight and facilitate growth of *Ulva*.

⁴ <https://weatherspark.com/y/82961/Average-Weather-in-Cape-Town-South-Africa-Year-Round>

Paddle-raceways are typically stocked with 1 – 2 kg *Ulva* per m⁻² of the pond surface area, as this has been shown to be optimal for both the nitrogen content and production of *Ulva*⁵. Tanks are harvested almost daily to provide feed for abalone and to maintain optimal stocking densities in the raceways. Exceeding optimal stocking densities not only leads to a reduction in production of *Ulva*, due to shading and insufficient nutrient availability, but can put excessive strain on the paddlewheel in the raceway. Seawater and *Ulva* are circulated through the raceway by a centrally located paddlewheel, which keeps *Ulva* suspended in the water column and vertical migration of *Ulva* improves exposure to sunlight. Circulation of water in the *Ulva* raceways also ensures a constant supply of cool, aerated water for the growing abalone. Effluent water from the 42 abalone raceways in each cluster is gravity-fed into its adjacent *Ulva* paddle-raceway, where it is bioremediated by *Ulva* and 50 % of this bioremediated water is recirculated back to the abalone tanks once it has been mixed with 50 % fresh seawater in the sump at the end of the paddle-raceway.

2. INTEGRATED SEA URCHIN-ULVA SYSTEM

Buffeljags Abalone Farm has recently adapted the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA process to produce a new (novel) high value species, the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. The pilot commercial urchin-*Ulva* IMTA system at the site consists of five 8.5 m³ fiberglass raceway tanks (Figure 5), which have identical dimensions to the abalone raceway tanks (Figure 5A), that are interconnected with a 14,000 L D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway (Figure 5B) and a 14,000 L sump. The system is fitted with a drum-filter, protein skimmers and a heat-pump to maintain optimal water quality and a constant temperature of ca. 25 °C. The entire system is housed within a tunnel to further conserve heat. This design is necessary for the farming of a tropical species in the temperate environment, where Buffeljags Abalone is located.

⁵ Neori, A., Krom, M.D., Ellner, S.P., Boyd, C.E., Popper, D., Rabinovitch, R., et al., 1996. Seaweed biofilters as regulators of water quality in integrated fish-seaweed culture units. *Aquaculture* 141, 183-199.

Figure 5. Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system to produce sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacunculata*) at Buffeljags abalone. The photograph shows (A) the sea urchin raceway tanks and (B) the *Ulva* paddle-raceway systems. ©M. Cyrus.

Effluent water exiting each of the urchin tanks flows into the D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway, after passing through the drum-filter to remove larger particulates. The bio-remediated seawater exiting the *Ulva* paddle-raceway enters the sump before being recirculated back to the sea urchin tanks. Water in the sump is consistently circulated through the heat pump to maintain a constant temperature of ca. 25 °C. The water replacement in this system, with fresh incoming seawater from the adjacent ocean, is 10 % per day. The sea urchins in each tank are grown in 6 mm oyster mesh baskets (L × W × D: 0.8 × 0.5 × 0.5 m), with 20 baskets suspended in each raceway. Seawater is circulated through the tanks and *Ulva* paddle-raceways, ensuring a constant supply of

heated, aerated water for the growing sea urchins. Animals are fed on a combination diet consisting of freshly harvested farmed *Ulva lacinulata* and formulated feed containing 20 % dried *Ulva lacinulata*⁶.

3. SPECIES PRODUCTION

3.1. FARM MANAGEMENT

The management of a land-based pump ashore IMTA production system includes a number of daily/weekly/monthly activities that are common to all the production species.

Routine Operations (daily/weekly/monthly)

- Daily feeding of animals.
- Daily inspection and monitoring of animal health and behaviour must be conducted. This is most frequently done when feeding animals and cleaning systems. Health assessment should include observations of feed response (feeding less or more), animal behaviour (noting any abnormal behaviour), general appearance of animals (e.g., colour, visual marks, shell integrity, or sores/lesions, loss of spines), and presence of any external parasites (e.g., shell boring worms).
- Daily removal of any moribund or dead animals from the baskets. Records of daily morbidity/mortality must be kept, as this could provide early warning of emerging problems (e.g., disease, poor nutrition, adverse water quality) in the system.
- Daily/weekly recording of environmental parameters on site, including pH, salinity, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and nutrients such as phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, and ammonia.
- Daily system checks and system maintenance (when required).

⁶ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., De Wet, L., Macey, B.M., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high-quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45, 159–176.

- Daily maintenance of biosecurity check points (e.g., footbaths, hand sanitizers, sterilisation of equipment, including boots and overalls) and ensure all areas are tidy and free of clutter.
- Other routine activities on the farm include grading of animals to reduce stocking densities to optimal levels within baskets. Grading on most abalone farms generally occurs once every 3 – 4 months^{7,8}. Grading of sea urchins occurs weekly. The specific procedures for each of these activities, including maintenance of *Ulva* density in raceways, are discussed in detail below under production of each species.

Recordkeeping

- Stocking and feeding records to be updated as required.
- Record of daily/weekly environmental parameters.
- Record of daily morbidities and mortalities.
- Biosecurity records updated daily.
- Record of health checks/visits carried out.
- Site visitors log updated as required.

3.2. SOUTH AFRICAN ABALONE (*Haliotis midae*)

Haliotis midae is a marine mollusc belonging to the phylum Mollusca, a diverse group of organisms that includes, amongst others, the chitons, clams, snails, squids, and octopuses. There are approximately 100 species of abalone worldwide that are found in tropical, temperate, and cold waters, ranging in depth from the low tide line to depths exceeding 30 meters⁹. However, of all these species, only fifteen are commercially

⁷ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed ingredient: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health and gut microbiome of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD thesis, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 203pp.

⁸ Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁹ Bevelander, G., 1988. Abalone: Gross and fine structure. The Boxwood Press, Pacific Grove, California.

exploited¹⁰. In South Africa, there are five endemic species of *Haliotis* (*H. midae*, *H. parvum* L., *H. spadicea*, *H. queketti*, and *H. speciosa*) that occur along specific regions of the coastline¹¹. Of these, only *Haliotis midae*, known locally as 'perlemoen', is of commercial significance and has been commercially exploited since 1949¹².

The South African abalone aquaculture industry is small in comparison to certain global aquaculture industries, but the country is nevertheless the third-largest producer of cultured abalone worldwide after China and South Korea¹³. Abalone is by far the most successful aquaculture sub-sector in South Africa, in terms of value, and was comprised of 14 farms in 2021 that collectively produced around 2500 tonnes of abalone (fresh weight). Most of these farms have their own hatchery and do not rely on an external seed supply, with the hatchery phase of production taking ca. 9-months to complete and grow-out ca. another 2 – 3 years depending on the size of the final product (Figure 6), which typically ranges from 100 – 140 g (wet weight). All current commercial abalone farms in South Africa are land-based pump-ashore systems, with five of these farms operating integrated systems where they grow the green macroalga *Ulva lacunculata* in the abalone effluent. This practice allows for partial recirculation, bioremediation of effluent water and production of a supplementary feed for the abalone.

¹⁰ Britz, P.J., 1990. Global status of abalone aquaculture. In Perlemoen farming in South Africa. (Ed) Cook, P. Mariculture association of South Africa. pp 20–26.

¹¹ Branch, G. M., Griffiths, C. L., Branch, M. L., Beckley, L. E., 1994. Two Oceans. A guide to the marine life of Southern Africa. David Philip Publishers, South Africa.

¹² Tarr, R. (1992) The abalone fishery of South Africa. In Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture. (Ed) Shepard, S.A., Tegner, M.J., del Preo, G. Blackwell Scientific Publication, Oxford. pp 438–447.

¹³ <https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/south-africa-abalone-farming-goes-gold/>.

Figure 6. Production cycle of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. ©DFFE & UCT.

Standard Operating Protocols (SOPs) to produce many of the commercially important abalone species, as well as other marine gastropods, have been described in detail by Hahn¹⁴. However, since abalone aquaculture in South Africa only started in the early 1990's, this handbook contains limited information on the production, particularly grow-out technologies, of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. Regardless, most information in the "Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine molluscs" is still highly relevant to the production of *H. midae* and will provide a good initial guide to prospective abalone farmers.

The SOP outlined in this document includes some of the information provided in the Hahn (1989) handbook, but mostly incorporates information derived from an extensive review of published literature on *H. midae*, unpublished information obtained from student theses (when available on online library databases) and the practical knowledge gained at IMTA lab SA. The cultivation and husbandry practices for

¹⁴ Hahn, K.O., 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

Tripneustes gratilla, the new high valued invertebrate that has been introduced at IMTA lab SA, will be discussed in detail in this manual. Similarly, the cultivation and the husbandry practices for *Ulva*, grown in the integrated abalone-*Ulva* and urchin-*Ulva* IMTA systems at Buffeljags Abalone Farm, will be discussed. For additional detailed information on broodstock management, spawning, larval rearing, larval settlement, and weaning of *Haliotis midae*, please refer to Genade¹⁵, Visser-Roux¹⁶, and the FAO 'Training Manual on Artificial Breeding of Abalone'¹⁷.

Conditioning, Spawning and Seed Production

• Broodstock collection and conditioning

Haliotis midae generally do not spawn when mature/ripe individuals are collected from the wild, so a hatchery broodstock population must be established and conditioned using specific protocols to ensure that animals can be spawned successfully on a regular basis¹⁸. When collecting broodstock from the wild, it is highly recommended that broodstock animals are collected as close to the production facility as possible to establish a base population that resembles the genetic profile of the surrounding wild populations. If it is not possible to collect broodstock animals close to the hatchery/production facility, then animals from the same genetic stock should be sourced. These measures will ensure minimal genetic impact in the event of the escape of animals from the farming systems. It is also recommended that the base population be made up of sufficient numbers of broodstock (nmales - nfemales = 50 - 75) that are sourced from the surrounding wild populations in a random manner¹⁹. Most wild collected broodstock are approximately 15-years old, with an average length and weight of 20 ± 5 cm and 1.5 ± 0.5 kg, respectively¹⁶.

¹⁵ Genade, A.B., Hirst, A.L., Smith, C.J., 1998. Observations on the spawning, development and rearing of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. South African Journal of Marine Science 6, 3-12.

¹⁶ Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

¹⁷ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

¹⁸ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. Aquaculture Research 32:863-874.

¹⁹ Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE), Permit: Specific Conditions for Abalone, 2023.

Male and female broodstock animals must be housed separately in the holding facility and be tagged to facilitate management of animals and/or spawning events in the hatchery.

Several methods have been proposed for conditioning broodstock animals, but the most common approach is to provide optimal living conditions (tailored to the ecology of the species) and to feed animals *ad libitum*²⁰ with suitable feeds. *H. midae* broodstock are generally kept at a constant temperature of ca. 16 – 18 °C under fluorescent lights that are set to provide a 12:12 day. Males and females are maintained in separate small holding tanks (generally 40 – 50 L fiberglass or plastic tanks – to facilitate removal of the animals when spawning and cleaning) at a low stocking density of ca. 3 – 5 individuals per tank²⁰. Each tank is supplied with constant air and filtered (0.45 – 1.0 µm) seawater and cleaned regularly (2 – 3 times per week). Water in each of the holding tanks is replaced approximately 2 – 3 times per hour, and animals are generally fed a diet of natural seaweed consisting mainly of kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) and *Ulva*, but other seaweeds (e.g., *Gracilaria*) may also be provided dependent on their availability. A conditioning period of at least 1-month is required when animals are maintained under the conditions described above²¹.

New broodstock animals (F1 and beyond) are selected based on production parameters such as above average growth, shell condition, and general health. Although Tarr²² showed that abalone from the wild reach 100 % sexual maturity at around 7.2 years, it has been demonstrated that abalone kept under cultured conditions mature earlier and 100 % sexual maturity may occur as early as 3 years of age²¹. Newman²³ demonstrated that there is a linear relationship between fecundity and animal weight, with egg production per individual in the order of several million.

20 Hahn, K.O., 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press, Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

21 Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

22 Tarr, R., 1992. The abalone fishery of South Africa. In Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture. (Ed). Shepard, S. A., Tegner, M. J., del Preo, G. Blackwell Scientific Publication, Oxford. pp 438–447.

23 Newman, G.G., 1966. Movement of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. Division of Sea Fisheries: Investigational Report, 56, pp 1–20.

- **Spawning**

Abalone hold matured eggs for 3 – 6 months and can be spawned and eggs artificially collected using various external stimuli. Common stimuli include rapidly increasing water temperature, subjecting abalone to a sudden change in pH, treating water in the holding tanks with UV-light, which releases hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), or by addition of H₂O₂ directly to the water in the holding tanks²². One of the most commonly used methods for inducing abalone to spawn in hatcheries is by administering H₂O₂ to the water in holding tanks at a concentration of ca. 25 mg/kg, due to the fast and inexpensive nature of the procedure. In South Africa, most farms initially treat the water in the holding tanks with sodium hydroxide to increase water pH before addition of H₂O₂ ca. 15 minutes later. Abalone are exposed to the H₂O₂ for ca. 3 hours, before tanks are emptied and washed out to remove residual chemicals that could be toxic to the gametes²⁴ and refilled with fresh filtered seawater. Once filled, water flow is switched off to prevent dilution of gametes when spawning commences²⁵. Male abalone generally start to spawn after 4 hours and females after 6 hours⁵⁰. Following spawning, the quality of the released gametes should be carefully examined and the concentration of released sperm and eggs measured and adjusted accordingly. Visser-Roux²¹ determined that a sperm concentration of 50,000 sperm/mL and egg concentrations of ≤50 eggs/mL produced the highest hatch-out rates for *H. midae*. It was further shown that while fertilisation volume did not influence fertilisation success, fertilisation potential of the eggs did decrease with time, with eggs older than 100 minutes exhibiting lower fertilisation potential than eggs fertilised earlier. It is recommended that eggs are fertilised within 60-minutes following release. Following fertilisation, eggs are carefully washed to remove excess sperm and other debris. Fertilisation success is then determined under a light microscope (which generally exceeds 80 %) and fertilised eggs are transferred to hatch-out tanks. Spawners should be matured for a further 80 days prior to a second spawning event. Under such conditions, the number and quality of released eggs are ensured²⁶.

²⁴ Morse, D.E., Duncan, H., Hooker, N., Morse, A., 1977. Hydrogen peroxide induces spawning in mollusks, with activation of prostaglandin endoperoxide synthetase. *Science*, 196, pp 298-300.

²⁵ Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

²⁶ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

- **Hatch-out, larval rearing and settlement**

Hatch-out trays are generally shallow plastic containers filled with filtered (0.45 – 1.0 µm) seawater maintained at the same temperature as the broodstock holding tanks, to prevent temperature shock to transferred eggs (Figure 7a). Trochophores (Figure 7b) tend to concentrate at the surface of the plastic containers (negative geotaxis), and healthy veliger's (Figure 7c) congregate in vertical columns and repeatedly (every few minutes) tumble to the bottom of the tanks, scatter and regroup to reform new columns. Development from cleavage through to hatch-out normally occurs after 12-hours post-fertilisation and at 24-hours post-fertilisation the veliger larvae are transferred to larval rearing tanks. Other developmental stages of *H. midae* include: The inflate-shell veliger larvae (torsion; 207×265 µm) with retractor muscle (Figure 7d); Operculate veliger (pre-eye spot) (Figure 7e); Operculate veliger larvae (pre-eye spot) with retracted velum (Figure 7f); Crawling and settling stage (Figure 7g); Peristomial growth (Figure 7h); Circular-shell post-larvae (± 600 µm) (Figure 7i); Whole shell with no respiratory pores (Figure 7j); Juveniles showing dietary pigmentation on shell (Figure 7k); Juveniles of approximately 1-year of age (Figure 7l)²⁷.

Generally, the upper water layer of the hatching tank is collected and transferred to the larval rearing tanks as this contains the actively swimming, healthy larvae, while the underdeveloped or abnormal larvae at the bottom of the hatching tanks are flushed.

Figure 7. Developmental stages of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. ©Genade et al., 1988²⁸.

^{27, 28} Genade, A.B., Hirst, A.L., Smith, C.J., 1988. Observations on the spawning, development and rearing of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. South African Journal of Marine Science 6:3-12.

Once the veliger larvae are transferred to the larval rearing tanks, their metamorphosis and growth should be closely monitored. Larval development of *Haliotis* sp. is temperature dependent, with development occurring faster at higher temperatures²⁹. The larval development rate is measured by the time required for larvae to exhibit features that are distinctive to each stage (Figure 7), with settlement, metamorphosis, and deposition of the peristomal shell marking the transition from larval to post-larval development.

Larval rearing normally takes place in conical fiberglass or plastic tanks that are filled with filtered and sterilised seawater maintained at the same temperature as the broodstock rearing tanks (specific to the physiological requirements of the species being cultivated). The temperature of the water added to the rearing tanks should be within ± 1 °C so the transferred trochophore larvae are not killed by thermal shock. Aeration is generally not used in the larval rearing tanks as this can cause injury to the fragile larvae. For many Haliotid species, a larval density of approximately 300 larvae/L is recommended³⁰. The rearing tanks with the newly hatched trochophore larvae are maintained in a dark, temperature-controlled room until the larval shell is completely formed. The progress of larval development is summarised in Figure 7 above and takes approximately 5 – 7 days before the crawling and settling stage (Figure 7g) is reached. It is at this stage that larvae are moved to settlement tanks containing settlement plates precoated with an appropriate settlement substrate.

Induction of settlement is a critical step in the cultivation of *Haliotis* sp. During larval rearing, from fertilisation to veligers competent to settle, survival rates can be as high as 95 %, whereas survival rates of ca. 10 % are common during the transition from planktonic veliger to benthic juvenile³¹. Competent larvae display distinctive behaviours, including repeated upward swimming and sinking behaviours as they search for a suitable (inducing) substrate to settle on.

²⁹ Hahn, 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

³⁰ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

³¹ Hahn, 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

When a suitable settlement substrate is provided, the larvae will change shape several times before the spat begin to actively graze on the benthic diatoms provided on the plates. Settlement plates are generally made from flat or corrugated plastic sheets that have been pre-coated or seeded with either naturally occurring benthic diatoms or specific strains of diatoms that have been cultured in the hatchery. Benthic diatoms commonly used in abalone hatcheries include species of *Cocconeis*, *Nitzschia*, *Navicula* and *Amphora*³¹. Some hatcheries also use plates that have been grazed by juvenile abalone, which results in the succession of a secondary diatom community and a layer of polysaccharide mucus — a known settlement inducer for abalone. Settlement plates are prepared 2 – 3 weeks in advance of settlement by suspending the plates in a slurry of the diatom(s) that is poured into the settlement tanks. Settlement tanks used at different hatcheries can vary substantially in size and shape, but generally consist of rectangular fiberglass tanks in which the vertical settlement plates can be suspended. Indoor tanks should have sufficient lighting above the tanks to facilitate growth of the benthic diatoms and optimal coating of the plates with the benthic diatoms. For some *Haliotis* spp., the density of benthic diatoms on the settlement plates is recommended to be ca. 3000 cells/mm² for optimal settlement and survival³⁰. Once the competent larvae are added to the settlement tanks, the tanks should be maintained under constant lighting (to facilitate growth of the benthic diatoms, gentle aeration should be provided and there should be a daily exchange of water. Juvenile stocking density should be ca. 400 – 500 spat/m². Growth of the benthic diatoms on the plates should be carefully monitored during this phase of cultivation and occasional shading (e.g., by covering tanks with 50 % shade netting) may be required to control the growth of the benthic diatom communities. Water quality in the tanks must be monitored daily. Newly settled larvae can feed on benthic diatoms measuring between 5 – 10 µm during the first ca. 2 weeks and after ca. 20 days the spat are capable of consuming diatoms of 20 µm³².

When the juveniles reach a size of ca. 1.5 mm shell length (SL), which takes approximately 3 months for *H. midae*, the animals are transferred from the settlement plates (de-plated) to juvenile rearing tanks. These tanks are typically shallow rectangular fiberglass tanks

32 <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

equipped with suitable housing, such as PVC half-round piping, to provide refuge for the juveniles. Tanks are provided with constant aeration and flowing water maintained at the temperature of 15 – 18 °C. During this phase of production, the juveniles are fed on a diet consisting of formulated feed (1 – 4 mm pellet size, depending on size of juveniles) or seaweeds (e.g., *Gracilaria* and *Ulva*). Uneaten food and excrement at the bottom of the tanks must be removed daily before new feed is administered. Juvenile *Haliotis midae* are maintained in these tanks until they reach a size of approximately 16 – 18 mm SL, which takes ca. 6 – 7 months, before they are moved to the grow-out platforms on the farm.

Feed & Nutrition

As with most intensive farming operations, feed constitutes a major proportion of the production costs on South African abalone farms. Abalone on most farms in South Africa are typically fed various combinations of wild harvested kelp *Ecklonia maxima* (Figure 8A) or formulated feed (Figure 8B)^{33,34}. Of these, kelp is still the major feed on most farms and wild harvests for this purpose reached a peak of ca. 7000 tonnes (fresh) in 2011³⁵. Harvests have since dropped, partly due to the increased use of formulated feed on abalone farms, but also because of the use of other seaweeds, such as *Ulva* and *Gracilaria*, that are cultivated on certain farms (Figure 8C and D, respectively). There are currently five integrated seaweed–abalone farms in South Africa that do this and collectively grow almost 2500 tonnes of *Ulva lacinulata* per annum, mostly in abalone effluent, to use as a feed for abalone³⁶.

33 Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

34 Troell, M., Robertson–Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on–farm seaweed production and socio–economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1–4):266–281.

35 Rothman, M.D., Anderson, R.J., Kanjengo, L., Bolton, J.J., 2020. Trends in seaweed resource use and aquaculture in South Africa and Namibia over the last 30 years. *Botanica Marina* 63:315–325.

36 Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (*Ulvaceae*, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed–abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 2023:1–12.

Figure 8. Photographs of typical feeds administered to cultured abalone *Haliotis midae* in South Africa. (A) Wild harvested kelp *Ecklonia maxima*, ©J. Bolton. (B) Formulated feed, ©Marifeed. (C) Sea lettuce *Ulva lacinulata*, ©Viking Aquaculture. (D) *Gracilaria* sp. ©J. Bolton.

None of this *Ulva* grown on South African abalone farms is currently sold for other purposes³⁷. There are also a few farms that grow *Gracilaria* in tanks as feed (Figure 8D), mostly for juvenile abalone in the hatchery and weaning phases, and production is estimated to be around 600 tonnes (wet weight) per annum³⁸. Formulated feed use on South African

³⁷ Bolton, J.J., Cyrus, M.D., Brand, M.J., Joubert, M., Macey, B.M., 2016. Why grow *Ulva*? Its potential in the future of aquaculture. *Perspectives in Phycology* 3(3):113-120.

³⁸ Rothman, M.D., Anderson, R.J., Kanjengo, L., Bolton, J.J., 2020. Trends in seaweed resource use and aquaculture in South Africa and Namibia over the last 30 years. *Botanica Marina* 63:315-325.

abalone farms was estimated to be around 200 tonnes (dry weight) in 2004³⁹. However, production of abalone has practically doubled since then, from 833 tonnes in 2006 to 1,656 tonnes in 2019⁴⁰, and it is projected that the use of formulated feed has increased proportionally with this increase in production. Formulated feeds, which are relatively high in protein (Figure 8B, 26 – 34 %), are preferred by most South African abalone farmers as they are regarded as fundamental to the growth of abalone in intensive systems and because of their convenience to farm operations and management⁴¹. Most of the formulated feed used on South African abalone farms is produced locally by two feed manufacturers' — Marifeed (Pty) Ltd.⁴² and Specialized Aquatic Feeds⁴³. These formulated feeds contain mainly fishmeal, defatted soybean meal, starch, vitamins, and minerals⁴⁴. Both fishmeal and soybean meal are included as it has been shown that a combination of these ingredients results in faster growth of abalone than diets containing fishmeal as the sole protein source^{45, 46}. More recently, there has been an increase in the inclusion of seaweeds, such as kelps (mostly *Ecklonia maxima*), *Ulva* and to a lesser extent *Gracilaria*, as alternative protein sources and primarily for their use as functional feed ingredients⁴⁷.

39 Troell, M., Robertson-Andersson, D., Anderson, R.J., Bolton, J.J., Maneveldt, G., Halling, C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4):266-281.

40 Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE) Aquaculture 2020 Yearbook, South Africa.

41 Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863-874.

42 <https://marifeed.com/>.

43 <https://www.specialisedaquaticfeeds.com>.

44 Troell, M., Robertson-Andersson, D., Anderson, R.J., Bolton, J.J., Maneveldt, G., Halling, C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4):266-281.

45 Riddin, N.A., 2013. Growth and gonad size in cultured South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, South Africa.

46 Wu, Y., Kaiser, H., Jones, C.L.W., 2019. A first study on the effect of dietary soya levels and crystalline isoflavones on growth, gonad development and gonad histology of farmed abalone, *Haliotis midae*. *Aquaculture International* 27:167-193.

47 Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

Research has also shown that mixed diets, for example combinations of seaweeds or formulated feed supplemented with fresh seaweed(s), produce better growth rates than single-species diets⁴⁸.

Since abalone are nocturnal feeders, they are generally fed daily late in the afternoon on most abalone farms to promote optimal uptake of feed(s) and reduce leaching of ingredients from formulated feeds. Previous studies have shown that feeding rates for *H. midae* are rapid, averaging 0.45 – 0.48 % body weight per hour over a 24-hour period, with the bulk of the feed consumed between 18H00 and 24H00⁴⁹. On most abalone farms in South Africa, including Buffeljags Abalone, formulated feeds are added on top of the feeding plates, whereas seaweeds such as kelp and *Ulva* are added below the feeding plates between the vertical plates within each basket. During the night, abalone will move onto the top of the feeding plates to consume the formulated feeds. On farms where *Ulva* is provided as feed, it is either grown in paddle-raceway systems receiving abalone effluent and/or fertilised at least once a week. The crude protein levels of effluent-grown or fertilised *Ulva* have been reported to range from 7.8 – 25.8 %^{50,51,52} and are consistently higher when compared to that of wild harvested kelp (9.73 %). At Buffeljags Abalone, crude protein level of *Ulva* grown in abalone effluent ranges between 18 – 22 % and varies with season, being higher in the summer months when temperatures are higher. Kelp is harvested from the wild and farmers in South Africa require a Right from the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) to harvest. Alternatively, kelp is procured from an

48 Naidoo, K., Maneveldt, G., Ruck, K., Bolton, J.J., 2006. A comparison of various seaweed-based diets and formulated feed on growth rate of abalone in a land-based aquaculture system. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 18(3-5):437-443.

49 Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863-874.

50 Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Maneveldt, G.W., Naidoo, K., 2011. Effects of wild and farm-grown macroalgae on the growth of juvenile South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus. *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 36(3):331-337.

51 Shuuluka, D., Bolton, J.J., Anderson, R.J., 2013. Protein content, amino acid composition and nitrogen-to-protein conversion factors of *Ulva rigida* and *Ulva capensis* from natural populations and *Ulva lactuca* from an aquaculture system, in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 25, 677-685.

52 Queirós, A.S., Circuncisão, A.R., Pereira, E., Válega, M., Abreu, M.H., Silva, A.M.S., Cardoso, S.M., 2021. Valuable nutrients from *Ulva rigida*: modulation by seasonal and cultivation factors. *Applied Sciences*. 11(13):6137.

existing Rights holder near the farm. Harvesting of *Ecklonia maxima* for abalone as feed involves the cutting of fronds during low tide and is generally done from boats⁵³.

Numerous studies have investigated daily feed intake for *H. midae*^{54, 55, 56}. Feeding rates can vary from 0.3 – 0.5 % body weight (BW) per day, and will depend on the type of feed, system type and environmental conditions. For example, Britz et al. (2001)⁵⁷ reported feeding rates of 0.35 – 0.4 % BW/day for abalone fed formulated feed and demonstrated a reduction in feeding rates with increasing size of abalone. Conversely, abalone fed with kelp (*E. maxima*) exhibited slightly higher feeding rates of ca. 0.48 % BW/day, which is comparable to the feeding rates (0.48 % BW/day) of abalone fed a mixed diet of formulated feed supplemented with either kelp or *Ulva*. One of the main formulated feed suppliers in South Africa, Marifeed (Pty) Ltd. recommends that abalone farmers start by feeding 0.3 % of the abalone's body weight per day, and if all the feed is consumed within 24 hours to increase the daily feeding rate⁵⁸. "The supplementation of macroalgae into the diets of farmed abalone is done ad lib under standard production methods" on most S. African abalone farms⁶³. However, Brand (2023)⁵⁶ clearly demonstrated that much as 60 % of the formulated feed administered to abalone daily can be supplemented with either *Ulva* or *E. maxima* without negatively altering specific growth rate, shell growth, or condition factor of farmed abalone. He further demonstrated that feeding small amounts of seaweed improved overall consumption of feeds, highlighting the advantages of a mixed feeding regime, and providing additional support to previous research on this topic/species.

53 Troell M., Robertson-Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4):266-281.

54 Britz, P.J., Hecht, T., Mangold, S., 1997. Effect of temperature on growth, feed consumption and nutritional indices of *Haliotis midae* fed a formulated diet. *Aquaculture* 152:191-203.

55 Francis, T.L., Maneveldt, G.W., Venter, J. 2008. Determining the most appropriate feeding regime for the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus grown on kelp. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 20:597-602.

56 Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacinulata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

57 Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863-874.

58 https://marifeed.com/choosing-your-feed/#tips_on_feeding.

Stocking Density

Animals in intensive farming systems are generally kept at densities that far exceed what would normally be found in nature, which is necessary for achieving optimal production and economic yields. *Haliotis midae* in the wild have been reported to occur at densities ranging from 82 – 133 g/m², but farmed abalone are kept at far higher stocking densities of ca. 2 kg/m²⁵⁹. Suboptimal stocking densities are considered one of the major stress attributing factors in intensive aquaculture, resulting in increased competition for space and food and will also adversely impact water quality in the tanks, as well as animal condition, growth, and survival rates⁶⁰. Optimal stocking density will differ from farm to farm and depends on a variety of interrelated factors, including the farming system utilised (e.g., flow-through vs. recirculation), the flow-rates achievable within the raceway systems, size class of animal, feed administered on the farm and its quality, and the environmental conditions at the specific site.

The stocking density of abalone on most farms in South Africa is generally expressed as the percentage of available surface area (ASA) in a basket that can be covered by the abalone, and this is then frequently translated to a kg/basket value for practical purposes. To increase the available surface area, each basket is fitted with vertical plates that are made from PVC and separated by plastic dividers (Figure 4). Stocking density on abalone farms generally ranges from 16 – 18 % of the ASA in a basket, but “may be increased until a size dependent threshold is reached at which growth rates and animal health may be reduced”⁶¹. Flow rates within raceways tanks will depend on the stocking density and should increase with increasing stocking density to avoid adverse impacts on growth through competition for space and degradation of water quality. Nicholson⁶⁰ studied the effects of varying stocking density (16 %, 20 %, 22 % and 24 % of ASA) on different size classes of abalone (15 – 35 g, 45 – 65 g, and 70 – 90 g starting weight) and demonstrated a reduction in weight gain with increasing stocking density for all size classes of abalone tested. Conversely, food conversion ratio (FCR) and condition factor were not significantly affected.

⁵⁹ Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁶⁰ Nicholson, G.H., 2014. Towards understanding the effects of stocking density on farmed South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc, Department of Ichthyology, Rhodes University, Grahamstown 79pp.

Most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket during the grow-out phase of production. Once every 3 – 4 months, animals are graded into size classes (small, medium, large, or rejects), and re-stocked at 10 kg/basket. Damaged abalone are generally grouped as rejects, which are removed from the general production for alternative uses (most frequently used as product for canning). The density per basket is readjusted to 10 kg/basket following every sorting event to account for abalone growth, which is projected to be approximately 1 kg/basket/month on most abalone farms⁶². These adjustments are made to optimize space allocated to growing abalone and the management of feeding regimes to ensure maximum yields as measured by weight of the abalone produced.

Optimal Environmental Ranges

The commercially exploited South African abalone *Haliotis midae* is distributed from St Helena Bay on the west coast to just north of Port St Johns on the east coast of Southern Africa⁶³. All the abalone farms in South Africa fall within the natural range of *Haliotis midae* (Figure 9), apart from the northern Cape farms (Diamond Coast Abalone and Port Nolloth Seafarms, where *H. midae* does not occur naturally but conditions are still suitable for growth), so the animals are adapted to the environmental conditions of the coastal waters that are pumped ashore to supply the farmed animals⁶⁴.

⁶¹ Meusel, E., Menanteau Ledouble, S., Naylor, M., Kaiser, H., El Matbouli, M., 2020. Gonad development in farmed male and female South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, fed artificial and natural diets under a range of husbandry conditions. *Aquaculture International* 30:1279-1293.

⁶² Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacinulata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

⁶³ Simpson, B.J.A., 1994. An investigation of diet management strategies for the culture of the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa.

⁶⁴ Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

Figure 9. Distribution of mariculture farms along the South African coast, with the location of abalone farms depicted by the green lines/dots. ©DFFE.

Temperature

Temperature is regarded as the primary environmental factor affecting the physiology of abalone, directly affecting oxygen levels and feed consumption, ammonia excretion, growth, and survival rates⁶⁵. For cultured abalone, these factors can significantly impact the production and profitability of the aquaculture operation. Wild abalone are frequently found in water temperatures ranging from 12 – 13 °C, the minimum mean monthly temperature range on the west coast of South Africa⁶⁵, and up to a maximum of 23 – 26 °C, which is the seawater temperature range for Haga Haga (Eastern Cape Wild Coast of South Africa, 60 km east of East London) during the peak of summer (around February) — where the species occurs naturally and where the most northerly based commercial abalone farm (Wild Coast Abalone) is located (Figure 9). Britz et al. (1997)⁶⁵ demonstrated that a temperature range of 12 – 20 °C is physiologically optimal for the production of *H. midae* (Table 2), with growth, feed conversion

⁶⁵ Britz, P.J., Hecht, T., Mangold, S., 1997. Effect of temperature on growth, feed consumption and nutritional indices of *Haliotis midae* fed a formulated diet. *Aquaculture* 152:191-203.

ratio, and protein efficiency ratio increasing from 12 to 20 °C and then declining sharply at temperatures above 20 °C. Abalone maintained at temperatures at and above 22 °C exhibit visible signs of stress and tend to “walkout” of the water and occupy the upper portion of the baskets — sides of the baskets above the water line and on top of the feeding plates. When farms experience warm seawater temperature events (>20 °C), it is recommended that a feed with a lower protein content is used. The typical protein content of feeds formulated for abalone are ca. 34 %. Green et al.⁶⁶ demonstrated a reduction in mortality for abalone fed formulated feeds with a 22 % protein content during elevated temperature. Feeding protein rich formulated feeds to abalone maintained at water temperatures exceeding 22 °C has been shown to be detrimental to the health of cultured abalone, leading to a condition known as “bloat” that is caused by an increase in microbial activity in the digestive tract of abalone⁶⁷. When water temperatures increase, the solubility of oxygen in the water column also decreases. Oxygen consumption rates and the relative energy consumed by individual abalone also increase⁶⁸.

Table 2. Optimal environmental ranges for growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* in land based partially recirculating systems.

|
NUTRIENTS |
|---|--|--|--|---|
| 12 – 20 °C | 30 – 35 psu | >90 % (7 – 8 mg.L ⁻¹) | 7.7 – 8.2 | FAN < 7.5 µg.L ⁻¹ |

⁶⁶ Green, A.J., Jones, C.L.W., Britz, P.J., 2011. The protein and energy requirements of farmed South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. cultured at optimal and elevated water temperatures. *Aquaculture Research* 42(11):1653–1663.

⁶⁷ Macey, B.M., Coyne, V.E., 2005. Improved growth rate and disease resistance in farmed *Haliotis midae* through probiotic treatment. *Aquaculture* 245(1–4):249–261.

⁶⁸ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

Dissolved oxygen

Dissolved oxygen concentrations in abalone aquaculture systems in South Africa can fluctuate between 7.2 – 8.2 mg O₂/L and often depends on the distance of the animal or basket from the tank inlet and time of day⁶⁹. *Haliotis midae* is a nocturnal feeder, with the bulk of the feed administered to the animals consumed between 18H00 and 24H00⁷⁰. During feeding, more oxygen is consumed and there is an increase in excretion of waste products (CO₂ and ammonia). Oxygen consumption of *H. midae* also increases linearly with increasing temperature⁶⁹. Other factors affecting the levels/utilisation of dissolved oxygen in the water are stocking density and oxygen supply (e.g., water flow rate, aeration efficiency, temperature-dependent oxygen solubility)⁷¹. Vosloo and Vosloo (2013)⁷¹ assessed organismal (rates of oxygen consumption and ammonia excretion) and cellular (heat shock protein expression, antioxidant enzymes) responses of juvenile and adult *H. midae* exposed to low (6.5 mg/L), intermediate (7.6 mg/L) or high (8.5 mg/L) oxygen levels and showed that juvenile and adult abalone reacted differently to changes in environmental oxygen levels. Juvenile *H. midae* exhibited an apparent insensitivity to moderate changes in ambient oxygen, supporting observations for juvenile *H. laevisgata* exposed to 81 and 117 % of oxygen saturation⁷². Conversely, adult *H. midae* had increased DNA damage under hypoxic and hyperoxic conditions. Under more extreme hypoxia condition (ca. 60 % saturation), decreased oxygen consumption rates can result in histopathological changes (e.g., necrosis and changes in mucus cell structure) in gills, as demonstrated for juvenile *H. laevisgata*⁷². Based on these findings, it is suggested that optimal oxygen levels for the cultivation of *H. midae* should be maintained between 7 – 8 mg/L (Table 2).

69 Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

70 Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. Aquaculture Research 32:863–874.

71 Vosloo A, Laas A, Vosloo D, 2013. Differential responses of juvenile and adult South African abalone (*Haliotis midae* Linnaeus) to low and high oxygen levels. Comparative biochemistry and physiology. Part A, molecular and integrative physiology, 164(1):192–199.

72 Harris, J.O., Maguire, G.B., Edwards, S.J., Johns, D.R., 1999. Low dissolved oxygen reduces growth rate and oxygen consumption rate of juvenile greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevisgata* Donovan. Aquaculture 174:265–278.

Salinity

The average salinity of seawater is around 35 g/L or practical salinity unit (psu), and Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions are the two primary constituents. An optimal salinity range of 30 – 35 psu is recommended for *Haliotis midae* (Table 2). Since all abalone farms in South Africa are land-based pump ashore systems that utilise large volumes of seawater for their cultivation systems (typically replacing 100 % of the water in each tank at least once every two hours), the salinity on the farm is normally dependant on the location of the abalone culture system, and the natural oceanic conditions, but do not vary significantly from 35 ± 1 psu.

Ammonia

The primary nitrogenous by-product of protein metabolism excreted by abalone is ammonia. In aqueous solution ammonia exists in equilibrium between its un-ionized (NH₃) and ionized (NH₄⁺) forms, with the sum of the two forms referred to as the total ammonia-nitrogen TAN (NH₃₋₄-N)⁷³. Of particular concern for farmers is the fraction of unionised ammonia (NH₃), expressed as free ammonia-nitrogen (FAN) in the water column⁷⁴, as it can more easily diffuse across cell-membranes and is hence regarded as more toxic⁷⁵. The ionisation of ammonia is driven by other water quality variables including temperature, pH, and salinity, with increasing temperature and pH resulting in a higher proportion of ammonia existing as FAN. Reddy-Lopata et al.⁷⁶ investigated the toxicity of FAN to *H. midae* following an acute (36-hour) exposure and demonstrated that juveniles (10 – 15 mm) and adults (100 – 150 mm) differed in their susceptibility to NH₃ — with a FAN concentration of 9.8 µg/L causing 50 % mortality in juveniles, whereas a higher concentration of 16.4 µg/L caused 50 % mortality in adults.

⁷³ Bower, C.E., Bidwell, J.P., 1978. Ionization of ammonia in seawater: effects of temperature, ph, and salinity. Journal Fish Research Board Canada 35:1012-1016.

⁷⁴ De Prisco, J. 2019. An investigation of some key physico-chemical water quality parameters of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system operating recirculation methodology in the Western Cape of South Africa. MSc in Applied Ocean Science, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 70pp.

⁷⁵ Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁷⁶ Reddy-Lopata, K., Auerswald, L. and Cook, P., 2006. Ammonia toxicity and its effect on the growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus. Aquaculture 261(2):678-687.

These authors further demonstrated that chronic (3-month) exposure of abalone to sub-lethal levels of FAN (7.4 µg/L; TAN of 0.56 mg/L) caused a 50 % reduction in growth of *H. midae* when compared with a control group (no ammonium chloride added). Conversely, chronic (± 2-month) exposure of the greenlip abalone *H. laevisgata* and green ormer *H. tuberculata* to FAN concentrations of 41 – 45 µg/L resulted in only minor reductions in growth and less than 2 % mortality for both species^{77,78}. Similarly, *H. midae* (80 g animals) exposed to ca. 60 µg/L FAN for a 48-hour period resulted in no mortality⁷⁹. Collectively, these studies indicate that exposure to high sub-lethal concentrations of ammonia retard growth of abalone and can lead to mortality. The general rule of thumb for aquarists is that FAN concentrations above 0.02 mg/L (20 µg/L NH₃) may be toxic to fish. According to the WWF 'Abalone Aquaculture Dialogue Standards' (2010), TAN concentrations should not exceed 0.6 mg/L. Based on the results of the acute and chronic ammonia toxicity and exposure tests conducted on *H. midae*, Reddy-Lopata et al.⁸⁰ suggest a safe FAN level for *H. midae* of below 7.5 µg/L (Table 2).

pH

The pH scale in a simplistic form is a measure of the amount of H⁺ ions in a solution and is a fundamental chemical characteristic of water. The pH of the seawater may become altered due to the production of H⁺ ions when CO₂ reacts with water to form a HCO₃⁻ molecule and a H⁺ ion⁸¹. Common seawater pH is 8.0, but abalone change the carbonate system by excreting CO₂ during respiration, which combines with water molecules to form carbonic acid. This carbonic acid formed rapidly

⁷⁷ Harris, J.O., Maguire, G.B., Handlinger, J.H., 1998. Effects of chronic exposure of greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevisgata* Donovan, to high ammonia, nitrite, and low dissolved oxygen concentrations on gill and kidney structure. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 17:683-687.

⁷⁸ Basuyaux, O., Mathieu, M., 1999. Inorganic nitrogen and its effect on the growth of the abalone *Haliotis tuberculata* Linnaeus and the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* Lamarck. *Aquaculture* 174:95-107.

⁷⁹ Yearsley, R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁸⁰ Reddy-Lopata, K., Auerswald, L., Cook, P., 2006. Ammonia toxicity and its effect on the growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus'. *Aquaculture* 261(2):678-687.

⁸¹ Smith, R.G., 1988. Inorganic carbon transport in biological systems. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part B* 90(4):639-654.

dissociates into HCO_3^- and H^+ , and the generation of H^+ then decreases the pH⁸². Exposure of juvenile greenlip abalone *Haliotis laevis* and blacklip abalone *Haliotis rubra* to low levels of pH (ca. 7.16) was shown to cause enlarged tubules and lumen of the kidney and abnormalities in the gill structures of the exposed abalone⁸³. More recently, Lester⁸⁴ demonstrated that chronic exposure of *H. midae* to reduced pH (7.66 ± 0.07) led to a reduction in animal growth and shell strength. Low pH and the associated changes in bicarbonate chemistry can also adversely impact shell quality and the sale price for live abalone on export markets, by reducing shell strength and increasing shell breakage as well as increasing the number of “shiny” shells caused by decalcification⁸⁵. The optimal pH to produce *Haliotis midae* is 7.7 – 8.2 (Table 2). However, because of the diurnal feeding, oxygen consumption and excretory patterns of abalone on farms, these values can and will fluctuate and fall outside of these ranges for short periods of time.

Handling

Handling of abalone is generally kept to a minimum on farms as it can cause stress and even injuries and may adversely impact feed consumption rates as well as growth of the abalone when done too frequently. Abalone are generally only handled when tanks are cleaned, which requires temporary removal of the baskets from the rearing tanks, and when the animals are graded and sorted, which requires longer term removal of baskets. Cleaning occurs 1 – 2 times per week and depends on the type of production system and locality of the farm. Farms utilising recirculation technologies (e.g., Buffeljags Abalone) and/or located in warmer areas (e.g., Wild Coast Abalone) tend to clean more frequently (twice per week), due to a higher accumulation of particulate organic matter (POM) and/or biofouling in the system. During cleaning of tanks, baskets are removed from tanks, briefly washed down with

82 De Prisco, J., 2019. An investigation of some key physico-chemical water quality parameters of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system operating recirculation methodology in the Western Cape of South Africa. MSc in Applied Ocean Science, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 70pp.

83 Harris, J.O., Maguire, G.B., Edwards, S.J., Hindrum, S.M., 1999. Effect of pH on growth rate, oxygen consumption rate, and histopathology of gill and kidney tissue for juvenile greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevis* Donovan and blacklip abalone, *Haliotis rubra* Leach. Journal of Shellfish Research 18(2):61-619.

84, 85 Lester, N.C., 2021. The interaction of acidification and warming on the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, and the potential for mitigation in aquaculture. PhD in Faculty of Science, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 178pp.

fresh seawater using a hose to remove debris attached to the baskets and dividers and immediately transferred to an open (clean) raceway tank close by if space is available on the farm — to minimise stress to the animals while the raceway tank is flushed and rinsed. Once all the baskets containing animals have been moved to a clean tank, the dirty tank is drained fully (by opening a valve at the base of the tanks that allows this water to be flushed to waste) and washed with a high-pressure hose. Cleaning of tanks is normally done on a rotational basis, so not all tanks are cleaned on the same day. Grading and sorting of abalone on the other hand only occurs once every 3 – 4 months on most abalone farms in South Africa. This process necessitates the removal of the abalone from the baskets and dividers, as the animals need to be graded, weighted, measured, and sorted — either by hand or using machinery. Animals are anaesthetised during this procedure to minimise stress and damage to the animals — specific procedures described below under section 5.2.2.6. Baskets are also more thoroughly cleaned, using an industrial high-pressure cleaner, during grading and sorting events.

Growth Monitoring

Growth is affected by many factors such as source of stock, density, type and amount of feed, water flow and quality, handling techniques, temperature, and the type of culture system. Regular monitoring of growth during each phase of the production cycle (e.g., hatchery, weaning, and grow-out; see Figure 6) is essential for tracking and managing the health of stock on the farm. During grow-out, most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket, and every 3 – 4 months abalone growth and stocking density is measured and recorded and the stocking densities in the baskets re-adjusted to 10 kg/basket. During grow-out, most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket, and every 3 – 4 months abalone growth and stocking density is measured and recorded and the stocking densities in the baskets re-adjusted to 10 kg/basket. This is done to optimise space allocated and management of feeding regimes to ensure maximum yields of the abalone produced. Basic procedure is as follows:

- The total basket weight (i.e., weight of basket with animals) is recorded, using an electronic balance, immediately after removing the basket from the raceway, to determine total animal weight gain in the basket over the growth period.

- Immediately after recording basket weight, the entire basket with animals is placed in a small tank/bucket containing anaesthetic — to assist with the removal of abalone from the basket walls and plate dividers. This is essential for abalone as they tend to pull down rapidly and tightly onto the surfaces of baskets and dividers when disturbed, which makes removal difficult⁸⁶. Mechanical removal of abalone without using anaesthetic is not practiced, as it is too time consuming, and can cause stress and injury to the animals. Anaesthetics commonly used on abalone farms include magnesium sulphate (effective concentrations are 4, 14 and 22 g/100mL for the size classes 5 ± 15, 20 ± 50 and 60 ± 90 mm shell length, respectively) or carbon dioxide: oxygen gas mixture (11.3 % : 88.7 %) delivered into the seawater at a rate of 2 L/min⁸⁷.
- Once anaesthetised and detached from the substratum, the abalone are graded into size classes (small, medium, large, or rejects) and counted before being returned to their respective baskets containing fresh oxygenated seawater to recover. The density of abalone per basket is readjusted during grading to 10 kg/basket before being returned to their respective raceway. Grading is either done by hand or using automated size graders.
- When grading by hand, a subpopulation from each basket is often individually weighed (using an electronic balance to the nearest 0.01 g) and measured (using a caliper along the longest length of the shell to the nearest 0.01 mm) to obtain more detailed growth data, whereas most automated size graders can record individual animal weights and store this information electronically.

⁸⁶ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. Aquaculture Research 32:863-874.

⁸⁷ White, H.I., 1995. Anaesthesia in abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 97pp.

Predator Control and Treatment

Disease/pest agents that have been identified from the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* include a range of opportunistic *Vibrio* species, such as *V. anguillarum*⁸⁸ and *V. alginolyticus*⁸⁹; the oomycetes *Haliphthoros milfordensis*⁹⁰ and *Halioticida noduliformans*^{91, 92}; polychaetes, such as the sabellid worm *Terebrasabella heterouncinata*^{93, 94} and several *Boccardia* and *Diploydora* spp.⁹⁵; a sessile peritrichous ciliate (*Mantoscyphidia midae*)⁹⁶; as well as gut and digestive gland protozoa⁹⁷.

None of the above-mentioned parasites, except for *H. noduliformans*, have caused large scale mortalities on commercial abalone farms (regarded as production diseases that do not require reporting to the WOA), but can adversely impact production, sales and ultimately farm profits. Infestations with these parasites are routinely monitored, during grading and cleaning events on the farm (as described above) through visual observation of shells (worm tunnels in shells, broken shells, lack of new ridges, shiny shells) and controlled through strict adherence to

⁸⁸ Macey, B.M., Coyne, V.E., 2005. Improved growth rate and disease resistance in farmed *Haliotis midae* through probiotic treatment. *Aquaculture* 245(1-4):249-261.

⁸⁹ Dixon, M.G., Hecht, T., Brandt, C.R., 1991. Identification and treatment of a *Clostridium* and *Vibrio* infection in South African abalone, *Haliotis midae* L. *Journal of Fish Diseases* 14:693-695.

⁹⁰ Hatai, K., 1982. On the fungus *Haliphthoros milfordensis* isolated from temporarily held abalone (*Haliotis sieboldii*). *Fish Pathology* 17:199-204.

⁹¹ Macey, B.M., Christison, K.W., Mouton, A., 2011. *Halioticida noduliformans* isolated from cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa. *Aquaculture* 315:187-195.

⁹² Greeff, M.R., Christison, K.W., Macey, B.M., 2012. Development and preliminary evaluation of a real-time PCR assay for *Halioticida noduliformans* in abalone tissues. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* 99:103-117.

⁹³ Gray, M.S., Kaiser, H., 2007. Settlement pattern and survival of a shell-infesting sabellid polychaete, *Terebrasabella heterouncinata*, on South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, fed two diets. *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 32:275-279.

⁹⁴ Ruck, K.R., Cook, P.A., 1998. Sabellid infestations in the shells of South African molluscs: implications for abalone mariculture. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 17:693-699.

⁹⁵ Boonzaaier, M., Neethling, S., Mouton, A., Simon, C.A., 2014. Polydorid polychaetes (Polychaeta: Spionidae) on farmed and wild abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa - an epidemiological survey. *African Journal of Marine Science* 36(3):369-376.

⁹⁶ Botes, H., 1999. Sessile ciliophorans associated with *Haliotis* species (*Mollusca: Archaeogastropoda*) from the south coast of South Africa. University of the Free State 229pp.

⁹⁷ Mouton, A., Gummow, B., 2011. The occurrence of gut associated parasites in the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, in Western Cape aquaculture facilities. *Aquaculture* 313:1-6.

biosecurity, helping to limit spread of the parasite within and between facilities, and good husbandry/sanitation practices, particularly on farms utilising formulated feed — which has been shown to increase prevalence of worms as uneaten feed provides a food source for the worms. Abalone tubercle mycosis in South Africa is the most recent disease diagnosed from *H. midae* in 2006 and caused large scale mortalities on at least three commercial farms⁹⁸. However, it is currently regarded as a production disease and effective containment has been achieved by destocking of affected raceways/facilities, sterilisation of equipment, removal, and decontamination of biological filter material (when present) and adherence to suitable fallowing periods. Moreover, strict adherence to biosecurity, optimal husbandry practices, and early detection and subsequent management are regarded as effective means to reduce the occurrence of this pathogen, as is the case for other production diseases.

Harvesting

Most abalone farms in South African focus on producing abalone which are ca. 100 – 140 mm in size, which take approximately 4 – 5 years to produce. Cultured abalone are a premium seafood delicacy that is mainly consumed in the Far East, and traded as either live, frozen, dried, or canned products. Prices for these products, produced by South Africa abalone farms, fetch on average US\$ 30–50/kg on Asian markets. When the abalone are ready for sale, they are moved to the processing facility on the farm, if the farm has its own fish processing establishment (FPE), or to the FPE nearest to the farm — where the abalone are processed for live export or into frozen, canned, or dried products. When transporting live abalone, transit times should be kept to a minimum and should not exceed 36-hours⁹⁹. Live abalone for long shipments (e.g., South Africa to China) are generally packaged into Styrofoam boxes that contain ice packs, to maintain a cool temperature during transit, as well as moist foam (to maintain a humid environment), and the boxes are filled with oxygen immediately prior to sealing and shipment. It is also recommended to starve and purge animals for 2 – 3 days prior to transportation to reduce stress and bloating (due to microbial activity

⁹⁸ Macey, B.M., Christison, K.W., Mouton, A., 2011. *Halioticida noduliformans* isolated from cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa. *Aquaculture* 315:187–195.

⁹⁹ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863–874.

in the digestive tract) of abalone and minimise the production of faecal matter/waste during transport⁹⁹. Temperature fluctuations during long shipments should also be kept to a minimum to avoid stress and mortality. Harvested animals are treated in a similar manner to animals during grading and sorting, with baskets containing abalone initially placed in a small tank containing anaesthetic to assist with the removal of abalone from the basket walls and plate dividers, which minimises stress and damage to animals. Abalone are also sorted according to size prior to packing (for live transport) as well as for frozen products, canning or drying (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Typical products from South African abalone farms, including (a) live, (b) frozen, (c) canned, and (d) dried.

3.3. SEA URCHIN (*Tripneustes gratilla*)

Sea Urchin Distribution, Life Cycle and Production Cycle

The sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* occurs globally in tropical and subtropical regions, where broodstock animals can be collected from deep or shallow ocean floors along its distribution range (Figure 11) but are most abundant at 2 – 15 m offshore. Sea urchin life cycles

are characterised by two developmental stages: a free-swimming larval phase, and a benthic juvenile and adult phase¹⁰⁰ (Figure 12). Given that the sea urchin life cycle has been closed for aquaculture production^{101, 102}, careful consideration should be given to the different needs of the sea urchins at the respective phases of their life cycles. Briefly, the sea urchin larval phase starts after a fertilised egg hatches and a prism-shaped larva forms. For the first seven days of development, *T. gratilla* larva have access to the nutrients that were present in the egg (maternal reserves)^{103, 104}, but larvae will require active feeding for the duration of larval rearing (25 – 40 days) with microalgal feeds. The larva will go through various larval phases, first developing four arms after approximately 5 days, which will be followed by an eight-armed phase after 20 days. During larval development the larvae remain in the water column, where they feed on microalgae to fuel this development. At the end of larval rearing, larvae undergo metamorphosis into benthic juveniles upon exposure to settlement cues¹⁰⁵. Juvenile sea urchins take approximately three weeks to develop the structures of an adult sea urchin and are considered mature after one year (Figure 12).

100 Toha, A.H.A., Sumitro, S.B., Hakim, L., Widodo, N., Binur, R., Suhaemi, Anggoro, A.W., 2017. Review: Biology of the commercially used sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Echinoidea: Echinodermata). *Ocean Life* 1:1-10.

101 Scholtz, R., Bolton, J.J., & Macey, B.M., 2013. Effects of different microalgal feeds and their influence on larval development in the white-spined sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *African Journal of Marine Science* 35:25-34.

102 Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., & Macey, B.M., 2015. The role of green seaweed *Ulva* as a dietary supplement for full life-cycle grow-out of *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Aquaculture* 446:187-197.

103 Brink-Hull, M., Cyrus, M.D., Macey, B.M., Rhode, C., Hull, K.L., & Roodt-Wilding, R., 2022. Dietary effects on the reproductive performance of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* I: Implications for broodstock conditioning. *Aquaculture*, 552:738035.

104 Byrne, M., Prowse, T.A.A., Sewell, M.A., Dworjanyn, S., Williamson, J.E., & Vaitilingon, D., 2008. Maternal provisioning for larvae and larval provisioning for juveniles in the toxopneustid sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Marine Biology* 155:473-482.

105 Dworjanyn, S.A., & Pirozzi, I., 2008. Induction of settlement in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* by macroalgae, biofilms, and conspecifics: a role for bacteria? *Aquaculture* 274:268-274.

Figure 11. *Tripneustes gratilla* distribution along tropical and subtropical regions (Adapted from Toha et al., 2017).

Figure 12. *Tripneustes gratilla* life cycle separated into the free-swimming larval phase, and benthic juvenile and adult phase as described in Toha et al. 2017. m: minutes, d: days, w: weeks.

Sea urchin production is therefore divided into (i) a hatchery phase where free-swimming larvae are raised until they undergo metamorphosis and (ii) a grow-out phase where sea urchins are fed optimal diets for growth, and gonads are developed until suitable for market (Figure 13). In the hatchery, broodstock animals need to be maintained to enable spawning and the collection of gametes (eggs and sperm). Eggs and sperm are combined to fertilise the eggs whereafter it takes 1 – 2 days until larvae hatch (Figure 12). Once hatched, larvae are transferred and raised in a controlled hatchery environment until deemed ready for settlement and metamorphosis. In the hatchery, a day:night cycle of 12h:12h should be maintained and water quality should be preserved using a protein skimmer, bio-filter, sand-filter and 100 µm filter bags^{106, 101}. Good incoming water quality is needed to maintain sea urchin larvae, as well as during grow-out, and therefore a land-based site should preferably be situated close to the sea. The juveniles are grown for roughly a month and can be fed the green seaweed *Ulva*, whereafter a land-based sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA grow-out system can be stocked when sea urchins reach a diameter of approximately 10 mm. Sea urchins are grown under natural light conditions during grow-out. When the urchins are grown in integrated systems with *Ulva*, the light conditions should be carefully considered to allow for optimal access to light and growth of the *Ulva* in the integrated system. Seawater temperature is an important criterion for this sea urchin species, which grows optimally at 24 – 28 °C^{102, 107, 108}, but can tolerate temperatures up to 32 °C. These temperature conditions mean that the site ideally needs to be located where seawater is warmer or a heat pump (which is costly to run) needs to be used to warm the water. The species/strain of *Ulva* grown in the IMTA system also needs to be compatible with the rearing temperature of the sea urchins. Sea urchin production takes approximately one year from the larval stage to producing sea urchins that are ready for market (Figure 13). It should be noted that production methods for *T. gratilla* are not limited to the protocols outlined in this manual and other approaches have also proved successful¹⁰⁸, particularly with regards to the diet used at hatchery and grow-out stages^{101, 102}.

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¹⁰⁶ Brink-Hull, M., Cyrus, M.D., Macey, B.M., Rhode, C., Hull, K.L., & Roodt-Wilding, R., 2022. Dietary effects on the reproductive performance of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* II: Implications for offspring performance. *Aquaculture*, 553: 738034.

¹⁰⁷ Mos, B., Dworjanyn, S.A., Cowden, K.L., 2012. Potential for the commercial culture of the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in Australia. Rural industries research and development corporation (RIRDC) publication no: 12/052.

¹⁰⁸ Mos, B., Dworjanyn, S., 2020. Boosting the productivity of sea urchin aquaculture using advanced culture protocols and dietary intervention. *AgriFutures Australia* publication no: 21-143.

Figure 13. Land-based sea urchin production cycle consisting of a ca. 1-3 month hatchery phase followed by a 9-12 month grow-out phase. ©UCT & DFFE.

Broodstock Daily/Routine Operations

The daily operations will differ depending on production stage, i.e. hatchery vs. grow-out. In the hatchery, wild collected *Tripneustes gratilla* broodstock (80 – 150 mm test diameter) that have been sexed by inducing spawning after collection, can be maintained in small individual tanks (ca. 11 L) connected to a heated (24 – 25 °C) recirculating aquaculture seawater system (RAS). The daily system water replacement rate should be at least 30 % of the system volume, which is achieved by the addition of fresh seawater filtered to 1 µm. Each 11 L broodstock tank must be supplied with aeration and heated (24 – 25 °C) filtered (100 µm) seawater at a water exchange rate of ca. 300 – 360 tank volumes per day. This high flow rate ensures optimal water quality and health of the animals in the event of spawning (ensures gametes are flushed rapidly, thereby mitigating against risk of poor water quality). Broodstock animals should be maintained on conditioning diets for a minimum of three months prior to spawning. Wild broodstock are spawned on a rotational basis in laboratory setting.

Broodstock Conditioning (Feeding)

Feeding regimes will largely depend on the phase of production for sea urchins. Sea urchin broodstock can be conditioned on a mixed diet of seaweeds (*Ecklonia maxima* and *Ulva lacinulata*). Animals should be fed every second day to apparent satiation, with each seaweed species being alternated weekly. At each feeding, uneaten food is removed, and the tanks cleaned before adding fresh feed. The feeds used for broodstock conditioning impact larval growth, development and survival¹¹⁰ and the inclusion of seaweeds in broodstock conditioning feeding regimes has been found to benefit gametogenesis and egg quality¹⁰⁶. These benefits stem from the maternal nutrients invested in the eggs that will be used to fuel the early larval developmental stages, prior to the development of feeding structures and a digestive tract.

Broodstock Spawning

Supplies and equipment needed:

- Autoclaved 2 M potassium chloride (KCl) solution (14.92 g of KCl in 100 mL of sterile distilled water)
- 0.2 µm filtered autoclaved seawater maintained at 24 – 25 °C
- 1 mL syringes
- 26G×5/8" (0.45 × 16 mm) needles
- 4000 mL autoclaved glass beakers
- 1000 mL autoclaved glass beakers
- 500 mL autoclaved glass Erlenmeyer flasks – Wide neck
- 15 mL sample tubes
- Test tube rack to hold 15 mL tubes
- 100 µm sieve
- 60 µm sieve
- 37 µm sieve
- 500 mL long nozzle squeeze bottle (2)
- 100 µL pipette with tips
- Haemocytometer and cover slip for quantifying sperm
- Bogorov tray for egg quantification
- Compound Microscope (400× magnification)
- Dissecting Microscope (40× magnification)
- Cavity slides
- 1000 µL pipette with tips
- 100 µL pipette with tips
- Hatching tanks (number & size dependent on number of eggs)

Sea urchin spawning is induced by carefully placing a sea urchin aboral side down on a wide-necked Erlenmeyer flask (Figure 14) filled to the brim with 0.22 μm filtered seawater (25 °C) and injecting 0.5 mL 2M KCl into the peristomial membrane (Figure 15). Care should be taken to avoid injecting the gonad or other tissues/organs. However, this is not the only method for spawning induction and other methods including thermal, saline or mechanical shock^{109,110} have also been reported.

Figure 14. Sea urchins placed aboral side down to collect gametes in 500 mL flask.
©M. Brink-Hull.

Figure 15. Sea urchin aboral side down showing injection site (peristomial membrane).
©M. Cyrus.

¹⁰⁹ Gago, J.M., Luis, O.J., Repolho, T.R., 2009. Fatty acid nutritional quality of sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck 1816) eggs and endotrophic larvae: relevance for feeding of marine larval fish. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 15:379.

¹¹⁰ Osanai, K., 1975. Handling Japanese sea urchins and their embryos. In: Czihak, G. (Ed.), *The Sea Urchin Embryo. Biochemistry and Morphogenesis*, Springer Verlag, Berlin, pp 26–40.

When gamete release starts, the below steps can be followed:

1. When gamete release begins, note the time, and ensure that gametes are entering the Erlenmeyer flask and not spilling out. Separate the sexes for ease of monitoring:

- Males will release sperm, which is distinguishable by its milky white colour and suspended distribution in the flask (Figure 16A).
- Females will release eggs, which are generally orange to yellow in colour, and will sink in clumps to the bottom of the flask (Figure 16B).

Figure 16. Male sea urchin (left) releasing sperm and female sea urchin (right) releasing eggs. ©M. Cyrus.

2. During spawning, regularly pour small amounts of filtered 24 °C seawater over the urchins to ensure they remain moist and ensure the flask is completely full and gonadal pores covered.

3. If an urchin does not start to produce gametes after 5 min, gently remove the urchin from the top of the flask and swirl or invert it gently, then place it back on the flask. If an urchin still does not initiate spawning, inject the remaining 0.5 mL KCl solution. If the urchin still does not spawn after an additional 5 min, remove the urchin and place it back in its respective broodstock holding tank.

4. Once an urchin has completed gamete release (Figure 17), remove the urchin and place it back into its respective labelled tank for recovery, ensuring high water turnover rates in case of additional gamete release during recovery.

Figure 17. Spawned sea urchins, where eggs and sperm can be seen on the bottom of the 500 mL flasks (front row: females; back row: males). ©M. Brink-Hull.

5. Inspect the collected gametes for general quality, urchins that produce low amounts of sperm or eggs should be discarded as gonads can be assumed immature.

6. Sperm from individual males should be passed through a 60 μm screen to remove unwanted particulates and collected in individual marked 1000 mL beakers. Samples of the individual urchin's sperm should be collected in 15 mL sample tubes and labelled for quality assessments.

7. Sperm samples should be assessed under a compound microscope at 400 \times magnification to confirm good motility.

8. After confirmation of sperm motility, equal quantities from up to five males should be combined in a single 4000 mL beaker and stored until used (within 1 h). Sperm from animals that do not exhibit efficient motility should be discarded and not combined with other male sperm. Sperm from individual males can be kept separate and individual crosses for each male and female conducted to avoid parental skews (one male dominating a spawning event).

9. Invert tubes gently to ensure even distribution of gametes before loading onto a haemocytometer. Sperm concentration of the mixed (or individual) male(s) should be determined using a haemocytometer at 400 \times magnification to calculate the concentration per mL.

Dilute (in seawater) to 1000× or 10,000× if necessary. Follow the manufacturer’s instructions to use the haemocytometer and use the below as a guide:

- a. Count all, or a representative sample, of the cells in the grid of 16 squares.
- b. In the event of cells on lines --- count cells on right and lower lines only.
- c. Calculations:

$$\frac{\text{Number of cells}}{\text{mL}} = \frac{\left(n \times \frac{16 \text{ Squares}}{\# \text{ of Squares Counted}} \right)}{0.1 \text{ mm}^3} \times \frac{10^3 \text{ mm}^3}{\text{mL}} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

where *n* = total number of cells counted count. The dilution factor part of the equation is a reminder to account for any dilution of your sample prior to counting.

10. Eggs from individual females should be filtered through a 100 µm screen to remove unwanted particulates while transferring them to individual marked 1000 mL beakers. Samples of the individual urchin’s eggs should be collected in a 15 mL sample tube and labelled for quality assessments.

11. Egg samples should be assessed under a microscope for each spawned female at 100× magnification. Egg health can be confirmed by the appearance of a uniform round shape with full and uniform internal texture. Only select females that produced eggs with a healthy appearance and discard eggs from individuals that are not.

12. Egg concentration for each spawned urchin should be determined by counting the number of eggs per mL using a Bogorov tray under a dissecting microscope at 30× magnification, dilute to 10× or 100× if necessary, prior to counting. Invert tubes gently to ensure even distribution of gametes before loading the Bogorov tray. Keep eggs separate until fertilisation.

13. For each urchin spawned, the volume of water and egg concentration per mL is used to calculate the total egg number. Use this value to determine the amount of sperm required for fertilisation at a ratio of 100:1 (sperm:eggs). Amount of sperm to add = [(egg concentration per mL x total volume of eggs in mL) x 100]/amount of sperm per mL]. Mix sperm into individual 1000 mL beakers containing individually spawned urchin eggs, stir gently and allow to stand for 10 min.

14. Confirm fertilisation success for each female by placing a drop of eggs onto a cavity slide and observing it under the microscope at 100× magnification. A fertilisation membrane (Figure 18) should be present on at least 95 % of the eggs. If found to be lower than this, discard these eggs.

Figure 18. Unfertilised and fertilised sea urchin eggs. ©M. Cyrus.

After fertilisation is confirmed, the below steps can be followed:

- 1.** The eggs should be rinsed with 0.22 µm filtered seawater to remove excess sperm on a 60 µm sieve, as they are roughly 80 µm in diameter and will remain on the sieve while the excess sperm is washed away.
- 2.** The collected fertilised eggs can be placed in tanks (ca. 90 L tank required for fertilised eggs from two females) containing 0.22 µm filtered seawater pre-heated to 25 °C and supplied with fine aeration (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Sea urchin egg hatching containers fitted with fine aeration and kept at 25 °C. ©B. Macey.

3. The eggs should hatch in 24 – 48 h, whereafter prism shaped larvae (Figure 20) will be visible when viewing larvae under a microscope.

Figure 20. Larval stages of *Tripneustes gratilla* (a) day 2, prism; (b) day 3, 2-arm stage; (c) day 6, 4-arm stage; (d) day 10, 6-arm stage; (e) day 18; 8-arm stage and (f) day 25, late 8-arm stage. ©M. Cyrus.

Sea Urchin Larval System Setup and Stocking

Larval rearing can be done using a static or flow-through system in either flat-bottom or conical tanks (Figure 21). For a static system, no banjo sieves are needed in tanks and water replacements should be done twice a week or as needed.

Figure 21. Larval rearing system with (A) flat-bottom or (B, C) conical shape. ©B. Macey & M. Brink-Hull.

Larval rearing system consists of:

- 8 × UV filters (55 W)
- Fine sand filter (3-Bag)
- 1 μm filter
- Bio-filter
- Protein skimmer
- Heat-pump
- Conical or flat rearing tanks
- 300 W rod heater per tank
- Airstone per tank or glass rods (0.5 cm diameter)
- 120 μm Banjo sieve per tank
- 200 μm Banjo sieve per tank
- 4000 mL glass beakers (4)
- 1000 mL glass beakers
- 15 mL sample tubes per tank
- Test tube rack
- 1000 μL pipette with tips
- 100 μL pipette with tips
- Haemocytometer and cover slips
- Bogorov tray
- Cavity slides
- Dissecting microscope (40x magnification)

Larval system stocking protocol:

- 1.** After larval hatching (24 – 48 hours post-fertilisation), hatching tanks should be gently cleaned of dead larvae (pink/red patches) that have accumulated on the bottom by siphoning with a narrow diameter pipe. This is done to reduce the transfer of dead larvae and subsequent bacterial growth associated with them.
- 2.** Homogenous water samples from each hatching tank should be collected and stored in marked 15 mL sample tubes for larval counting.
- 3.** Larval concentration (larvae/mL) should be calculated by using a dissecting microscope at 40X magnification to count the number of larvae in 1 mL aliquots within the Bogorov tray. Samples may need to be diluted 10x or 100x to accurately count the larvae.
- 4.** Conical rearing tanks fitted with 120 µm Banjo sieves on the outflows (in order to retain larvae within the tank during water exchanges) should be prepared with filtered heated seawater (~25 °C) from the rearing system and a 300 W rod heater to maintain temperature (~25 °C). The banjo sieves should be cleaned twice a week or when needed.
- 5.** Aeration should be provided at all times, with 0.20 µm filters attached to each tank's airline. Although fine aeration (airstones) can be used in larval rearing tanks, a diagonal thin glass rod (0.5 – 1 cm wide) attached to aeration tubing is a good strategy for maintaining optimal water circulation in the tank. A tap fitting on the aeration tubing should be used to maintain slow aeration.
- 6.** Photoperiod is maintained on a 12h:12h light:dark cycle.
- 7.** Check individual tank temperatures before transferring larvae into them.
- 8.** Healthy larvae should then be transferred from the hatching tanks to the prepared conical rearing tanks using the 4000 mL beakers and stocked at a density of approximately 5 larvae/mL. Lower starting stocking densities of 1 larvae/mL can help improve larval access to feed.
- 9.** If a flow-through system is used, the bottom of the conical larval rearing tanks should be briefly flushed every second day and the sides of the cone siphoned carefully using a long glass rod with a diameter of 0.5 – 1 cm, to remove dead larvae and uneaten food at the bottom

of the tanks. If a static system is used, a full tank replacement needs to be done twice a week by siphoning the tank water into a 100 – 150 µm sieve in a container that has already been filled with seawater at 25 °C. Open tap at the bottom of the tank to slowly drain water as the siphoning progresses. Thereafter the original tank that larvae were kept in should be thoroughly cleaned and refilled with fresh seawater at 25 °C before returning larvae. Be sure to gently rinse the sieve to ensure that no larvae were left on the sieve.

Sea Urchin Larval Rearing

Routine hatchery tasks include water quality monitoring (temperature, aeration, cleanliness and system functionality), tank water replacements (biweekly or as needed), daily assessment of larval development and larval counting to assess stocking density. Daily larval feeding requires continuous microalgal feed preparation, which requires growing microalgal cultures using F2-media (and sodium-metasilicate where appropriate), and quantification of microalgal cells prior to feeding the sea urchin larvae. Lastly, while raising larvae, which takes ca. 25 – 40 days, containers with settlement substrates need to be prepared and maintained until larvae are deemed competent for settlement.

Larval feeding can be done in two ways: (i) a gradual increase in the number of microalgal cells throughout the larval rearing period as described in steps 8 – 11, or (ii) feeding at a constant 10 000 cells/mL tank volume from day 2 of larval rearing by starting with a mixed diet of *Isochrysis* and *Chaetoceros* at 5000 cells/mL each, and including *Rhodomonas* towards day 7 of larval rearing and feeding approximately 3400 cells/mL of each microalgal feed (*Isochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, *Rhodomonas*).

Larval rearing procedure:

1. After 2 days of static water flow and no feeding, the larvae are fed on a diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*) at a ratio of 1000 cells/mL for 2 days. If running as a flow-through system for the remainder of the larval rearing period, tanks are supplied with fresh seawater from the rearing system during the night cycle at a replacement rate of 70 % per day.
2. Larval counts should be conducted every 2nd day during the rearing period to guide feeding rates.

3. On day 5, the larvae are fed an equal portion diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*) and *Chaetoceros muelleri* at a ratio of 2000 cells/mL. Feeding volume is increase daily by 500 cells/larvae for the next 4 days. Increase feeding rates if larvae show signs of insufficient feeding i.e. skeleton protruding from arms.

4. On day 10, larvae are fed an equal portion diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*), *Chaetoceros muelleri* and *Rhodomonas salina* at a ratio of 6000 cells/larvae. This is increased daily by 1000 cells/mL up until a maximum feeding rate of 10000 cells/mL.

5. If making use of a flow-through system: once larvae reach a size greater than 200 μm , the 120 μm Banjo sieves can be replaced with 200 μm sieves to reduce the blockage of the sieves by flushed algae.

6. Full water tank replacements should be performed twice a week in static systems but can be used in flow-through systems to improve rearing success. This is done by draining the contents of the tank into a 100 – 200 μm bucket sieve (sieve size depending on larval sizes) and collecting the concentrated larvae, which are transferred to a clean tank.

7. Larvae are reared as described above for approximately 30 days until considered competent to settle. However, it should be noted that larval rearing can continue for as long as 40 days. Larvae are deemed competent for settlement when the rudiment (large black structure in the centre of the larva in Figure 22A) is larger than 400 μm and/or when pedicellariae (tube feet) are observed. Larvae are then drained from the rearing tanks into a 200 μm sieve and concentrated for transfer to prepared settlement tanks (see preparation guide below).

Figure 22. Sea urchin larva (A, B) competent for settlement after 35 days of larval rearing and (C, D) after metamorphosis. ©M. Brink-Hull & B. Macey.

8. When these features are observed, larvae should be moved to a container pre-prepared with a settlement substrate as described above. Settlement success is improved by adding small amounts of *Ulva* (cut to small pieces in a blender).

Microalgal Feed and Settlement Substrate Preparation

Standard protocols to grow microalgae are available^{111, 112} and should be referred to in conjunction with the below instructions.

Equipment needed:

- Algal stocks: *Isochrysis/Tisochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, *Rhodomonas*
- Algal tubes/bags to bulk up microalgae
- F2 growth media (check expiry dates) at a concentration of 100 g/L
- Sodium metasilicate at a concentration of 40 g/L
- Measuring cylinder
- Siphon
- Haemocytometer
- Dissecting Microscope (40x magnification)
- Settlement tanks
- Settlement substrates (options): *Cocconeis*, *Ulvela*, *Nitzschia*

Microalgal feeds need to be prepared as described below prior to starting larval rearing to allow enough time for feeds to reach high cell concentrations (ca. 7 million cells/mL).

Microalgal feed preparation protocol:

1. Microalgal cultures (*Isochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, and *Rhodomonas*) should be continuously bulked up in 0.22 µm filtered seawater from stocks (Figure 23). Algal stocks should be used to first culture 2 L microalgae in autoclaved 0.22 µm filtered seawater using 150 mL of stock culture and F2 media at a concentration of 1 mL/L for all microalgal cultures, and 1 mL/L sodium metasilicate for *Chaetoceros*. Each bottle is fitted with aeration (glass tubing) and continuous light.

111 Helm, M., Bourne, N., 2004. Hatchery culture of bivalves. A practical manual. FAO Fisheries Technical Paper 471. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Rome, 2004.

112 Jaramillo, J.C., 1996. Microalgae Culture Protocol. Aquaculture Division Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institution Incorporated.

2. After 5 – 7 days, or when microalgal density has noticeably increased (checked with haemocytometer), the 2L bottles can be used to seed larger volumes of 50 – 70 L of 0.22 µm filtered seawater (Figure 23). To avoid contamination, the growth tubes/bags should be filled with 0.22 µm filtered seawater 24h before adding microalgae, supplied with aeration (glass rod) and should be treated with chlorine dioxide (e-oxide LQ).

Figure 23. Microalgal feed including (A) *Rhodomonas*, *Chaetoceros* and *Isochrysis*, and (B) bulked up *Chaetoceros* used to feed sea urchin larvae. ©M. Brink-Hull & B. Macey.

3. Once microalgae have been added to the larger volumes, F2 media and/or sodium metasilicate should be added at 1 mL/L.

4. Settlement substrates should be prepared at the start of larval rearing or earlier (e.g. *Ulvelia*). Diatoms such as *Cocconeis* and *Nitzschia* should be bulked up from stock cultures as described in step 2, with the addition of 1 mL/L F2 media and 1 mL/L metasilicate. Once noticeable growth is observed (5 – 7 days), the 2 L bottles can be used to seed a settlement container [90 L settlement containers (L x W x H: 80 x 42 x 26 cm)]. To avoid contamination, the settlement tanks should be filled with 0.22 µm filtered seawater 24h before adding microalgae, supplied with aeration and should be treated with chlorine dioxide (e-oxide LQ).

5. The settlement tanks can also be fitted with plastic racks to coat a higher surface area with the settlement substrate. To effectively coat racks, the racks should be turned on a weekly basis for improved access to light.

6. Once microalgae have been added, these tanks should be supplied with constant light, fine aeration and 1 mL/L F2 media and 1 mL/L metasilicate.

7. Larval metamorphosis is dependent on settlement cues, one of which is the presence of a suitable settlement substrate. *Ulvelva* settlement tanks show a high settlement success rate for sea urchins but requires sporulation to seed settlement tanks¹¹³. See the protocol outlined in Hannon et al. (2014) for more details.

Sea Urchin Deplating and Juvenile Growth

After settlement (metamorphosis) juvenile sea urchins are grown in the settlement troughs for ca. 1 month, while adding small amounts of the green seaweed *Ulva*. During this time, daily water quality assessments and cleaning is performed to remove faecal matter. Juvenile sea urchins are moved to grow-out tanks when they reach ca. 5 – 10 mm and are fed only *Ulva* for the first month of grow-out, whereafter kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) can also be fed (Figure 24).

Figure 24. (A, B) Juvenile sea urchins on settlement plates, (C) feeding on *Ulva* after deplating and (D) feeding on *Ulva* and kelp for early grow-out stages (1–2 months). ©B. Macey.

¹¹³ Hannon, C., Officer, R.A., Le Dorven, J., Chamberlain, J., 2014. Culture methods of live algal feeds for European aquaculture: optimising culture conditions for *Ulvelva lens*. *Aquaculture International* 22:1813–1822.

Sea Urchin Grow-out Daily Activities

When urchins are grown in land-based integrated systems where the sea urchin effluent water is linked to a paddle-raceway with *Ulva*, as in the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa, the daily activities include animal health and biosecurity assessments, tank cleaning to remove uneaten feed, feeding, system functionality (aeration, water flow, filters) assessments, system maintenance (when required), draining and cleaning *Ulva* paddle-raceway (when required). The *Ulva* required for feed is harvested daily and the raceways are monitored to ensure optimal functionality. The *Ulva* system is fully drained and cleaned every 2 – 3 months and restocked. Size grading is particularly important during early grow-out stages as sea urchin growth is fast at this stage and a high degree of variation in growth is generally observed, which if left unmonitored/ ungraded can lead to cannibalism by the larger animals, as well as limited access to feed for the smaller ones. During grading, animals that are noticeably larger or smaller are moved into new baskets with an optimal basket depth of 15 cm to ensure optimal access to feed¹¹⁴. The optimal stocking density for *T. gratilla* is estimated at a density of ca. 20 % basket internal surface coverage or 6 – 8 kg/m², with limited differences in animal performance¹¹⁴. This sub-tropical/tropical sea urchin takes approximately 9 – 12 months from settlement to reach a marketable size and animals are size graded throughout production (weekly-monthly or as needed) to maintain optimal stocking densities.

During grow-out, sea urchins are held in raceway tanks and are distributed into 6 mm mesh baskets to allow faecal material to fall through (Figure 25). These tanks are fitted with aeration and water is kept at ca. 25 °C at the South African IMTA lab using a heat pump. The seawater needs to be heated because of where the IMTA site is located, but a farm could be run without a heat pump further up the east coast of South Africa where the water temperatures are higher and *T. gratilla* naturally occurs.

¹¹⁴ De Vos, B.C., Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., 2024. Effect of basket height and stocking density on production of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*: insights and recommendations. Aquaculture International: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-024-01412-8>.

Figure 25. (A) Land-based sea urchin grow-out system, with (B) 6 mm mesh baskets subdivided into four where (C) sea urchins are feeding on *Ulva* and a formulated feed. ©B. Macey.

Sea urchins are fed daily, and the feeding regime used depends on the approximate age/size of the sea urchins. Sea urchin aquaculture is characterised by two main growth stages: somatic growth (first ca. 6 – 7 months) and gonad enhancement (last 3 – 4 months). Somatic (body) growth is characterised by an increase in body size while limited gonad growth/development is observed. During gonad enhancement the weight of the five gonads in the urchin test increases while there is a small degree of somatic growth. Sea urchin feeding regimes may also depend on the availability of seaweeds near the site. The seaweeds *E. maxima* and *U. lacunculata* have been successfully used to produce sea urchins (Table 3). In the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa a diet of IMTA-produced *Ulva* and a formulated feed containing 20 % *Ulva* have been tested based on previous works that show that 20 % dry *Ulva* (w/w) inclusion in formulated feeds improves feed palatability, acts as a source of carotenoids that contribute to the orange colouration of the gonads, and acts as a feeding stimulant for sea urchins, thereby promoting gonad development¹¹⁵. This formulated feed has a protein content of 25.69 %, a fat content of 2.31 % and a carbohydrate content of 43.75 %¹¹⁵ (Table 3). Sea urchins require moderate protein inclusion (20 – 40%) in diets to produce commercially viable gonads^{115, 116, 117}, with higher protein levels negatively impacting sea urchin growth rates¹¹⁸. This is attributed to the high energetic cost of metabolising protein. In terms of their carbohydrate requirements, it has been found that sea urchins display no difference in growth at a wide range of carbohydrate concentrations (21 – 39 %)¹¹⁹, and the 20U formulated feed falls within the optimal ranges for sea urchin gonad development.

¹¹⁵ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Scholtz, R., Macey, B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 21:578–591.

¹¹⁶ Akiyama, T., Unuma, T., Yamamoto, T., 2001. Optimum protein level in a purified diet for young red sea urchin *Pseudocentrotus depressus*. *Fisheries Science* 67:361–363.

¹¹⁷ Powell, M.L., Marsh, A.G., Watts, S.A., 2020. Chapter 4: Biochemical and energy requirements of gonad development in regular sea urchins. In Lawrence J.M. (Ed.), *Sea urchins: biology and ecology*, 4th Ed., Elsevier, Oxford, UK, pp. 51–62.

¹¹⁸ Eddy, S.D., Brown, N.P., Kling, A.L., Watts, S.A., Lawrence, A., 2012. Growth of juvenile green sea urchins, *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*, fed formulated feeds with varying protein levels compared with a macroalgal diet and a commercial abalone feed. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 43:159–173.

¹¹⁹ Heflin, L.E., Gibbs, V.K., Powell, M.L., Makowsky, R., Lawrence, J.M., Lawrence, A.L., & Watts, S.A., 2012. Effect of dietary protein and carbohydrate levels on weight gain and gonad production in the sea urchin *Lytechinus variegatus*. *Aquaculture* 359–359:235–261.

Table 3. Nutrients in recommended *T. gratilla* feeds (*Ecklonia maxima*, *Ulva lacinulata*, formulated feed with 20 % *Ulva* inclusion) as described by (a)¹²⁰ Smith 2007, (b)¹¹⁵ Cyrus et al., 2015 and (c)¹²¹ Shuuluka 2011. All estimates are expressed as % dry weight. n.d. not determined.

NUTRIENTS (% DW)	ECKLONIA MAXIMA	ULVA LACINULATA	FORMULATED FEED (20U)
Protein	11.00 ^a	18.31 ^b	25.69 ^b
Fat	1.16 ^a	0.38 ^b	2.31 ^b
Moisture (% ww)	79.39 ^a	80.60 ^c	9.61 ^b
Ash	19.41 ^a	32.66 ^b	13.89 ^b
Gross energy (MJ/kg)	n.d.	9.44 ^b	15.49 ^b
Fibre	41.34 ^a	6.02 ^b	4.75 ^b
Carbon/Carbohydrate	33.82 ^a	27.33 ^b	43.75 ^b

¹²⁰ Smith M.J., 2007. Seasonal variation in nutritional content of the kelp *Ecklonia maxima* on the west and south west coasts of South Africa, with reference to its use as abalone feed. MSc thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

¹²¹ Shuuluka, D., 2011. Ecophysiological studies of three South African *Ulva* species from integrated seaweed/abalone aquaculture and natural populations. PhD thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

During the somatic growth phase, sea urchins are fed *Ulva* or kelp three times a week at roughly 8.5 % and 10 %, respectively, of the average sea urchin body weight (bw) per feeding. Formulated feeds could also be fed for the full duration of grow-out, but as these encourage gonad development, these are better suited for the last months of grow-out where gonad enhancement should be prioritised. During gonad enhancement, formulated feeds are fed at 0.6 – 1.5 % bw three times a week, but can also be fed fresh seaweeds, such as the IMTA-produced *Ulva*, to improve water quality conditions. While feeding *Ulva* a feed conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.1 % can be expected, whereas formulated feed fed animals have an FCR of 0.4 %, as observed in the South African IMTA lab. It should be noted that it is generally considered best practice to only have one feed in the tank at a time to avoid the urchins showing a preference towards one feed, leaving the other to disintegrate and negatively impact water quality parameters.

Sea Urchin Growth Monitoring During Grow-out

During different grow-out stages (i.e. somatic and gonad growth), sea urchins should be measured and dissected to assess gonad development. Sea urchin body weight (g) and test diameter (cm) should be measured, which can be done using the open-source sea urchin measuring software developed in the ASTRAL South African IMTA lab¹²², or this can be performed manually with a scale and callipers. Sea urchins should be periodically dissected to assess gonad development. There are five gonads organised penta-radially inside the urchin test (Figure 26). From the exterior of the urchin, the gonads are situated in the areas of test where less tube feet can be observed. Therefore the sea urchins should be dissected by cutting on the areas of the test where tube feet are observed.

¹²² De Vos, B.C., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Batik T., Bolton J.J., 2023. Combining computer vision and standardised protocols for improved measurement of live sea urchins for research and industry. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries* 3:507–517.

Figure 26. (A) External and (B) internal anatomy of a sea urchin where five gonads are held inside an exoskeleton (test). ©Rupert and Barnes 1994.

Sea urchin dissection protocol:

1. Prepare dissection tray with scissors, tweezers, a spatula and seawater in a container.
2. Weigh animal and measure sea urchin diameter, and record information on datasheet.
3. Use scissors to cut into the peristome at an angle (Figure 27) whereby the scissors are pointed in the direction of test covered in tube feet.

Figure 27. Diagram of the oral side of a sea urchin where the incision should be made to dissect the animal.

4. Once the incision has been made, cut through to the top of the urchin test.
5. At the top, the direction of the cut should be changed to avoid cutting through a gonad (as depicted in Figure 27).
6. Using tweezers, remove the sea urchin intestines and other tissues.
7. Use the seawater to rinse any feed or loose tissue that may be present.
8. Repeat steps 6 and 7 until only the five gonads remain as depicted in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Dissected sea urchin with five gonads in the test cavity. ©M. Brink-Hull .

9. Use the spatula to scoop out the gonads into a weigh boat as depicted in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Sea urchin gonads that have been scooped out of the urchin test using a spatula. ©M. Brink-Hull.

10. Weigh the gonads and record the weight on a datasheet.

This method can be used to calculate the gonad somatic index (GSI) of the sea urchin, which represents the proportion of the sea urchin's weight that can be attributed to the gonad. $GSI (\%) = [\text{gonad wet weight (g)} / \text{total animal weight (g)}] \times 100$. For market purposes, a GSI of 20 % is aimed for, but can reach values as high as 35 %¹²³. The GSI is not the only indicator of market readiness, as gonad development and gonad colour are also good indicators and are important factors for the final monetary value of the product. Gonad development is dependent on the reproductive maturity of the sea urchin, where six sea urchin reproductive stages are described in literature, namely (1) recovery, (2) growing, (3) premature, (4) mature, (5) partly spawned and (6) spent. See the detailed guide by James and Siikavuopio (2012)¹²⁴ for more information of the staging of reproductive phases and

¹²³ Cyrus M.D., 2013. The use of *Ulva* as a feed supplement in the development of an artificial diet and feeding regimes to produce export quality roe from the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). PhD thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

¹²⁴ James, P., Siikavuopio, S., 2012. A guide to the sea urchin reproductive cycle and staging sea urchin gonad samples. The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research (NOFIMA), Norway.

the implications for market acceptability. Of these, the optimal reproductive stage for market is “growing” as firm sea urchin gonads containing few or no gametes are preferred. Therefore, histological approaches should be used to assess gonad development. A single gonad from each urchin will be randomly selected and transferred into Davidson's Fixative (per litre: 300 mL 95 % ethyl alcohol, 200 mL 100 % formalin, 100 mL glycerol, 100 mL glacial acetic acid and 300 mL distilled water) immediately following dissection and fixed for 48h, before being transferred into 70 % ethanol and processed for routine paraffin histology¹²⁵.

Stocking Density During Grow-out

Sea urchins should be stocked at roughly 6 – 8 kg/m² based on the experimental system in the IMTA lab South Africa or at 20 % basket surface coverage, but stocking densities should be decided on based on the site and the scale of the farming operation. This is particularly important in the case of a sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA where the farm is dependent on the green seaweed *Ulva*'s capacity for nutrient uptake. If this experimental system was upscaled to a similar size as the abalone system and stocked at 6.36 kg/m², a total of 0.75 tonnes of gonad could be produced per month in 42 tanks (357 m³) as determined in the studies conducted in the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa.

Record Keeping

Biosecurity checks are conducted daily on all animals (broodstock) in the hatchery, including system functionality, habitus, animal behaviour, mortality, morbidity and feed response. During larval rearing, daily observations are made of system functionality, larval density, feed density and larval development, and records of these parameters are kept. Water temperature is logged daily. Throughout grow-out, animal growth and health should be monitored, and daily assessments of animal health, feeding, habitus, morbidity, mortality and system functionality should be performed, and a record should be kept of these assessments.

¹²⁵ Bucke, D., 1989. Histology. In Austin B., Austin D.A. (Eds.), Methods for the Microbiological Examination of Fish and Shellfish, Ellis Horwood, Chichester.

Handling

Broodstock animals are only handled when necessary for tank cleaning or when used for spawning procedures. During spawning and larval rearing, strict biosecurity measures are put in place for any animal handling, with frequent use of 70 % ethanol to spray surfaces, glassware and hands before handling larval rearing equipment. After broodstock are spawned, they are held in a quarantine tank that is not linked with any other tank containing sea urchins to ensure that any residual spawning does not induce spawning of other animals.

Minimal larval handling is recommended where possible. Daily or every second day, 5 mL of the seawater containing larvae in each larval tank is collected to count larvae and assess larval development. Additionally, larvae are handled twice a week (if a static system is used) when water full tank exchanges are performed by siphoning larvae into a sieve (<100 µm for the first week and <150 µm for the remainder of larval rearing) and discarding the tank water so that the tank can be thoroughly cleaned, refilled with filtered 25 °C seawater and the sieve is gently placed in the newly filled tank to release larvae. The sieve is sprayed gently with seawater to move any remaining larvae back into the tank. The container used to collect all wastewater should be thoroughly cleaned between tanks while performing water exchanges.

During grow-out, sea urchins are handled to perform growth measurements and during weekly cleaning activities as baskets containing the urchins are removed from the tanks to completely drain and thoroughly clean them. To ensure that sea urchins spend limited time out of the water to avoid shock spawning, a clean tank can be prepared to simplify the cleaning process by moving the baskets into the clean tank before cleaning the previous tank. Similarly, the *Ulva* raceway and sump should be cleaned once a month or as needed.

Optimal Environmental Conditions

Though an optimal temperature range of 24 – 28 °C has been established for *T. gratilla* (Table 4), fast changes in temperature are more detrimental than absolute changes in temperature as this causes a stress response in the animals and has the potential to result in animals shock spawning. Optimal salinity for *T. gratilla* is 35 psu and dissolved oxygen of 90 % is considered optimal. Parameters such as free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) in the water column and seawater pH (optimal at a pH = 8.0 – 8.2) should be monitored to ensure optimal water quality, as this can affect sea urchin growth¹²⁶. Nutrient levels for FAN, total ammonia nitrogen (TAN), nitrite and nitrate should all remain low (as close to zero as possible) in the system, where high flow rates and the use of seaweeds in integrated systems can aid in removing these nutrients. It has been observed that *Tripneustes* have very low nitrogen emissions (Bas de Vos, pers. comm.), but FAN levels as low as 0.016 mg/L have been shown to reduce gonad size in other sea urchin species¹²⁷. Given that TAN levels are dependent on the water pH, no specific threshold has been established. If the pH is high, ammonia becomes un-ionised and toxic¹²⁸. In contrast, low pH can inhibit calcification and affect sea urchin production negatively as this is important for test (exoskeleton) development. Alkalinity is also an important consideration in sea urchin aquaculture systems and is considered optimal at 120 mg/L CaCO₃¹²⁹, as low alkalinities of < 20 mg/L may lower the buffering capacity of the seawater¹³⁰, which can negatively affect the FAN concentration. Lastly, a total suspended solids (TSS) threshold similar to that of the abalone standard of the Aquaculture Stewardship Council of less than 5 mg/L is recommended. Daily to weekly measurements of the relevant water quality parameters are performed, with the most important parameters including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and FAN.

¹²⁶ Shpigel, M., Erez, J., 2020. Effect of diets and light regimes on calcification and somatic growth of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla elatensis*. *Aquaculture* 735547.

¹²⁷ Siikavuopio, S.I., Dale, T., Foss, A., Mortensen, A., 2004. Effects of chronic ammonia exposure on gonad growth and survival in green sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*. *Aquaculture* 242:313-320.

¹²⁸ Mos, B., Byrne, M., Dworjanyn, S.A., 2016. Biogenic acidification reduces sea urchin gonad growth and increases susceptibility of aquaculture to ocean acidification. *Marine Environmental Research* 113:39-48.

¹²⁹ Boyd, C.E., Tucker, C.S., Somridhivej, B., 2016. Alkalinity and hardness: critical but elusive concepts in aquaculture. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 47:6-41.

¹³⁰ Hariyadi, S., Tucker, C.S., Steeby, J.A., van der Roeg, M., Boyd, C.E., 1994. Environmental conditions and channel catfish *Ictalurus punctatus* production under similar pond management regimes in Alabama and Mississippi. *World Aquaculture Society* 25:236-249.

Table 4. Optimal environmental conditions for the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in land-based aquaculture systems.

|
NUTRIENTS |
|---|--|--|--|---|
| 24 – 28 °C | 35 psu | > 90 %; > 6 mg.L ⁻¹ | 8.0 – 8.2 | FAN < 0.016 mg.L ⁻¹ |

Disease Control and Treatment

Sea urchin microbial consortia can be sensitive to stressors, including animal handling, grading, sudden environmental changes (e.g., system failures) or poor food quality. These stressors could result in a state of microbial dysbiosis and a reduction in beneficial microbes that may facilitate infection(s) by opportunistic pathogens(s), that may ultimately lead to mortalities¹³¹. Disease in sea urchins is characterised by spine loss and bald spots on the body (test) surface where the spines used to be. Daily animal health monitoring is used to avoid mortalities from these diseases as animals should be quarantined if infections are observed. Sea urchins also display cannibalism, particularly during early growth stages or when stocking densities are high. This can be avoided, to some extent, by ensuring consistent food availability by feeding *ad libitum* and by actively grading animals during early growth stages to ensure that animals with different size classes are not held in the same basket. Size grading will not only assist in avoiding cannibalism but will also result in faster growth rates for smaller animals.

Harvesting

Sea urchins are considered ready for harvesting when they are approximately 55 – 60 mm in test diameter, and if gonads are developed. Post-production processes include harvesting sea urchin gonads, assessing gonad quality, performing food safety tests and processing

¹³¹ Brink M., Rhode C., Macey B.M., Christison K.W., Roodt-Wilding R., 2019. Metagenomic assessment of body surface bacterial communities of the sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Marine Genomics* 47:100675.

the gonads for export. If transport is required for harvesting, animals should be gently placed in Styrofoam boxes that are lined with moist foam to place the sea urchins on. If animals spawn during transport, they can be rinsed with seawater upon arrival or placed in tanks with high water flow prior to harvesting.

Animals should be carefully monitored towards the end of grow-out as gonad quality, and its corresponding market value, is influenced by their reproductive phase. Gonads containing few or no gametes are preferred and therefore histological assessment of the gonads is recommended in the three months prior to harvesting. Product/gonad quality (firmness, colour, texture, taste) and food safety should be assessed prior to export to adhere to export food safety standards. High quality gonads with a bright and firm yellow or orange appearance have the highest market value¹³² and should therefore be exported as fresh product (harvested or as whole urchins)¹³³ (Figure 30). Lower quality products can be processed for market by baking, freezing, steaming and salting¹³⁴.

Figure 30. Fresh *Tripneustes gratilla* gonads/uni served on rice from animals produced at the DFFE Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point, Cape Town. ©M. Cyrus.

¹³² Robinson, S.M.C., Castell, J.D., Kennedy, E.J., 2002. Developing suitable colour in the gonads of cultured green sea urchins (*Stongylocentrotus droebachiensis*). *Aquaculture* 206:289-303.

¹³³ Stefánsson, G., Kristinsson, H., Ziemer, N., Hannon, C., James, P., 2017. Markets for sea urchins: a review of global supply and markets. NOFIMA: Icelandic food and biotechnology research and development. Report nr.: 10-17.

¹³⁴ Exploration Unlimited Incorporated. 2006. Sea urchin fishery profiles. Benchmarked competitiveness study of BC's sea urchin fisheries. Brentwood Bay, British Columbia, Canada: Exploration Unlimited Incorporated.

3.4. GREEN SEAWEED (*Ulva lacinulata*)

Choice of *Ulva* species/strain

A critical initial step in cultivating *Ulva* is the selection of the species to be grown. The *Ulva* on South African abalone farms was chosen not because it is a marketable product, but because of its fast consistent growth rates throughout the year, efficient ammonia uptake, and quality as feed for abalone. The identity of *Ulva* species has been the subject of much recent research: it is often not possible currently to accurately identify *Ulva* species by morphology, and DNA techniques are necessary¹³⁵. This has resulted in several different names having been used for the *Ulva* grown on South African abalone farms over the last 20 years. Most *Ulva* species grow attached on rocky seashores and reproduce by spore production regularly (commonly every two weeks, with a lunar reproductive cycle). Spore release causes significant portions of the *Ulva* thallus to deteriorate, with a large detrimental effect on production. A few species are capable of growth free-living (unattached) in nature, growing vegetatively without spore production, and some of these form large problem growths in sheltered waters, sometimes known as 'green tides'. Initial selection of *Ulva* material on South African abalone farms, beginning more than two decades ago, was from such free-living populations, and material has thus selected itself for growth in the systems (Figure 31). It has recently been shown in this project, by molecular barcoding, that material grown in abalone farms all around South Africa, in a number of biogeographic regions, is a single species, now correctly known as *Ulva lacinulata*¹³⁶ (Figure 32). Contaminants of other *Ulva* species do sometimes occur and can prove a problem (see later). *Ulva lacinulata* is also grown commercially, selected independently, in Europe, e.g. in Portugal¹³⁶.

¹³⁵ Tran, L.T., Vieira C., Steinhagen, S., Maggs, C.A., Hiraoka, M., Shimada, S., Van Nguyen, T., De Clerk, O., Leliaert, F., 2022. An appraisal of *Ulva* (Ulvophyceae, Chlorophyta) taxonomy. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 34:2689–2703.

¹³⁶ Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed–abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59:1272–1283.

Figure 31. *Ulva lacinulata* grown in a paddle raceway on a South African abalone farm. ©J. Bolton.

Figure 32. Morphology of *Ulva lacinulata* from Buffeljags Abalone Farm. B & C: Surface view and transverse section through edge region of the thallus. D & E: Surface view and transverse section through middle region of the thallus. ©Bachoo, 2021.

The successful growth of *Ulva* in land-based culture in various countries has had several factors in common:

- Generally foliose species of *Ulva* rather than tubular species (formerly *Enteromorpha*) are grown, often recorded as *Ulva lactuca* (a name used generally in the past for various species of foliose *Ulva* around the world), as well as *Ulva lacinulata*, *Ulva ohnoi*, *Ulva reticulata* etc., in various geographical locations.
- These are often collected initially in sheltered locations, from free-living populations.

- They are tested in the aquaculture systems in which they will be cultured, and the species which grow well in these systems can be cultured for long periods without problems with breakup from reproductive events. For example, Ryther (1982) in the USA did extensive culture work with a foliose *Ulva* which was given to him by a local aquafarmer who had found that it grew well in tanks¹³⁷.

Selection of a species/strain which grows well in any aquaculture system is critical to the success of *Ulva* cultivation but has not been studied in a particularly scientific way, as yet. Fort et al. (2020) have recently shown in strain selection experiments that laboratory growth rates can be higher in free-living 'green tide' populations¹³⁸, which matches the anecdotal information from aquafarmers growing *Ulva*. What is critical is production rates and *Ulva* quality in farm conditions, not in laboratory conditions, which are generally very different.

The *Ulva lacinulata* which is grown on South African abalone farms was produced from material originally collected in sheltered locations on the coastline, primarily Saldanha Bay on the west coast, although some farmers also collected from other locations (including Gansbaai and Simon's Town harbours). Initial data from Bachoo et al. (2023) suggests that *Ulva lacinulata* is rarely growing attached on South African seashores and was not found in a collection of foliose *Ulva* on seashores around Hermanus harbour, where *Ulva lacinulata* has been grown on local farms for many years¹³⁹.

Daily and Routine Operations

Ulva is grown on South African abalone farms in a year-round operation. It has good yield all year round, as a result of the mid-latitude position of the country. In a region with colder, darker winters (e.g. Northern Europe, Canadian Maritimes) this sort of year-round production would not be feasible, but it is practised in Southern Europe (e.g. Portugal,

¹³⁷ Ryther, J.H., 1982. Cultivation of macroscopic marine algae (Solar Energy Research Institute No. SERI/STR-231-1820). National Technical Information Service, US Department of Commerce.

¹³⁸ Fort, A., Mannion, C., Farinas-Franco, J.M., Sulpice, R., 2020. Green tides select for fast expanding *Ulva* strains. *Science for the Total Environment* 698:134337.

¹³⁹ Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (*Ulvaceae*, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59:1272-1283.

Helena Abreu, pers. comm.) and tropical Queensland, Australia (Rocky de Nys, pers. comm.). Monthly yields in South Africa tend to be higher in summer months¹⁴⁰. Daily routine involves visual monitoring of health and abundance. Darker green *Ulva* has higher nitrogen, and hence protein content¹⁴¹. Paddle raceways which become over-fouled by other benthic organisms, or where other floating organisms or sediment loads become a problem, are emptied and manually cleaned, followed by re-stocking.

Ulva is grown in abalone effluent directly fed from the abalone raceways, and as such does not need extra fertilisation at Buffeljags. In some South African abalone farms, the surface of the *Ulva* has occasionally become infected with a brown crustose seaweed (*Myrionema strangulans*), which can eventually cause thallus deterioration¹⁴². This tends to happen in Spring/early Summer when the *Ulva* is growing rapidly and may use up available nutrients. Evidence for this is that it has been experimentally shown that fertilisation can reduce the incidence of the *Myrionema*¹⁴². This has not proven a problem at Buffeljags Abalone.

In some South African abalone farms *Ulva* is grown as a feed component in seawater rather than in abalone effluent, in similar paddle raceways. In this case, nitrogen and ammonium fertiliser is added. At one farm, Shuuluka (2011)¹⁴³ reported that once a week each raceway pond is fertilised with 1.5 kg of ammonium sulphate and “Supergrow”® (P: 203 g/kg, S: 23.6 g/kg, Ca: 171.4 g/kg) in a ratio of 6:1. The fertiliser is added in the late afternoon after disconnecting the raceway pond from the rest of the system by closing the inlet- and outlet sluice gates. The amount of nutrients added was the same for all raceway ponds, and thus independent of seaweed density in the raceway ponds. Similar fertilisation happens ad hoc very occasionally at Buffeljags if *Ulva* growth is poor.

¹⁴⁰ Bolton, J.J., Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Shuuluka, D., Kandjengo, L., 2009. Growing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) in integrated systems as a commercial crop for abalone feed in South Africa: A SWOT analysis. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 21:575–583.

¹⁴¹ Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Wilson, D.T., Bolton, J.J., Anderson, R.J., Maneveldt, G.W., 2009. Rapid assessment of tissue nitrogen in cultivated *Gracilaria gracilis* (Rhodophyta) and *Ulva lactuca* (Chlorophyta). *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 34:169–172.

¹⁴² Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Potgieter, M., Hansen, J., Bolton, J.J., Troell, M., Anderson, R.J., Halling, C., Probyn, T., 2008. Integrated seaweed cultivation on an abalone farm in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 20:579–595.

¹⁴³ Shuuluka, D., Bolton, J. J., & Anderson, R. J. (2013). Protein content, amino acid composition and nitrogen-to-protein conversion factors of *Ulva rigida* and *Ulva capensis* from natural populations and *Ulva lactuca* from an aquaculture system, in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 25:677–685.

Optimal Environmental Conditions

Ulva lacinulata grown in these farms has relatively wide environmental tolerances, as shown by the fact that it is grown throughout the year commercially from Kleinsee to Haga Haga, with a range of monthly mean ambient seawater temperatures from 11.3 – 18.6 °C¹⁴⁴. In 15-day laboratory investigations (as *Ulva lactuca*) this species grew in a wide range of temperatures from 5 to 25 °C, died at 30 °C, with optimal growth at 15 – 20 °C¹⁴³. Growth at 25 °C was ca. 75 % of optimal. The latter showed promise for the same species being used at this higher temperature in integrated culture with the warm water urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*.

Ulva lacinulata also grew optimally at salinities of 25 to 40, showed some growth as low as 5, and survived 15 days in freshwater with added Provasoli nutrient medium¹⁴³. The latter can prove useful in brief washing with freshwater to remove certain biotic contaminants (e.g. mobile invertebrates such as isopods). In the same study the farm material was shown to have a higher light saturation for growth than two abundant local seashore species. Light is of course a critical factor for growth of photosynthetic organisms. The paddle wheel movement ensures continual flow so that individual *Ulva* plants are constantly circulated within the water column receiving alternately lighter and darker conditions. These paddle raceways were first used for microalgae such as *Spirulina*. In high density microalgal production units, microalgae alternate between light and complete darkness, whereas this is not the case with the *Ulva* in South African paddle raceways. It has been observed that light reaches the bottom of the *Ulva* paddle raceways, at Irvine & Johnson Cape Abalone in Gansbaai, even in winter in high density just before harvesting.

A major factor in algal growth is water nutrient concentration. It is not possible to state standard nutrient concentrations which limit growth, though, as the ability of a seaweed to take up nutrients is closely linked with water movement. Another critical factor in nutrient availability is nutrient replenishment, which in these systems depends on the water exchange rate into the *Ulva* paddle raceways. In still conditions, nutrient uptake over the thallus creates a nutrient deprived boundary layer over the surface of the seaweed. As water movement increases, growth increases until a saturation point is reached. In still culture in

¹⁴⁴ Bachoo, T., 2021. Characterization of *Ulva* (*Ulvaceae*, Chlorophyta) species cultured in commercial abalone farms in South Africa, and comparison with closely related wild species, using morpho-anatomical and molecular methods. MSc thesis, University of Cape Town.

the laboratory, growth is increased by using culture media with much higher levels of available nutrients (in specified nutrient media). The paddle raceways used to grow *Ulva* on abalone farms are a compromise solution. Seaweeds take up both major (especially dissolved inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus) and minor nutrients as well as dissolved gases (particularly carbon as dissolved carbon dioxide or bicarbonate for photosynthesis, and oxygen for respiration) from the water. The uptake of dissolved gases can be improved by aeration, but this is expensive to provide. The paddle raceways provide sufficient water movement for reasonable levels of nutrient uptake but are not optimal growth conditions. They are a financially viable option for *Ulva* efficient production, made more economical as one motor is used to run paddles for two adjacent raceways (Figure 33). It is considered by us to be generally ineffective to test strains of *Ulva* or other seaweeds for growth in laboratory systems and use the data to assume they are the best strains for growth in commercial systems.

Figure 33. Two adjacent paddle raceways at Buffeljags Abalone Farm, growing *Ulva lacinulata*. Note the single motor for two paddles, and the sump in foreground for mixing bioremediated abalone effluent with fresh seawater (normally 50 %). ©J. Bolton.

The initial abalone/*Ulva* system with 50 % bioremediated effluent recirculation was set up at I&J in 2005, designed by current VIKING manager, Nick Loubser. That system ran with a water exchange rate of ca. 13.3 water volume exchanges per day. This value would have to vary on different farms, both those recirculating bioremediated effluent and

those not, depending on the number of abalone producing the effluent running into the raceway. All these factors cannot be standardised and specified, as they will depend on various individual aspects of the systems. All abalone farms are subject to a large variety of different environmental conditions and abalone/seaweed culture techniques, and things like seasonal water flow rates will need to be tested on any new system. In South Africa the major upwelling system on the west coast ensures relatively high seawater nutrient concentrations in the ambient seawater, whereas in the North Atlantic many sites will have very low nutrient concentrations in the summer. This will affect required water turnover rates and possible need for fertilisation at certain times of year.

Grazer Control and *Ulva* contamination

Grazing animals are not a major problem in *Ulva* systems at Buffeljags. Occasionally colonies of small invertebrates trap sediment, but these are removed with routine paddle pond cleaning. In initial studies towards *Ulva* growth on South African abalone farms, there were some problems with mobile grazers. Various amphipod, isopod species and a keyhole limpet were recorded in *Ulva* tanks systems and could be managed, as in the current commercial systems, by regular cleaning. In the case of the keyhole limpets they could be treated by soaking for 20 minutes with freshwater, which the *Ulva* can survive¹⁴¹. The latter has not proven to be a problem in later commercial systems.

During the ASTRAL project some of the *Ulva* paddle ponds at Buffeljags, and also at the VIKING sister farm Diamond Coast Abalone at Kleinsee, became contaminated with a different *Ulva* species, morphologically identified as *Ulva linza* (sensu Stegenga et al. 1997)¹⁴⁵. This is a partially tubular species, formerly in the genus *Enteromorpha*, and it floats close to the water surface (Figure 34). This is problematic, as floating *Ulva* shades the *Ulva lacinulata* in the water column and the flotation means that it is not available if fed to the abalone. This is being successfully managed by emptying contaminated raceways and restocking with *Ulva lacinulata*.

¹⁴⁵ Stegenga, H., Bolton J.J., Anderson R.J., 1997. Seaweeds of the South African west coast. Contributions from the Bolus Herbarium 18:1-655.

Figure 34. Floating *Ulva linza* growing in a paddle raceway on a South African abalone farm. ©J. Bolton.

Stocking Density and Harvesting

Stocking density and harvesting regime for *Ulva* integrated with invertebrates depends on the main use of the *Ulva* in the system. In farms such as Buffeljags Abalone, where the main reason to grow *Ulva* is for bioremediation of effluent to enable partial water recirculation, then the *Ulva* must be stocked at relatively high levels and harvested often, generally weekly. In other farms in South Africa where the *Ulva* is grown predominantly as feed for the abalone, *Ulva* raceways are stocked at lower levels and fully emptied for harvest and restocked each month. The latter farms harvest different raceways in rotation to enable regular availability of *Ulva*, whereas at Buffeljags each raceway is partially harvested weekly (Figure 35). Harvesting is carried out manually at Buffeljags. At other South African farms where paddle raceways are fully harvested once per month, the raceway is emptied and *Ulva* is manually brushed to one end of the raceway for manual harvesting in crates.

At a system at I&J Cape Abalone, where paddle raceways are emptied monthly, each raceway “has an underground drainpipe which surfaces from the raceways on the sea side. During harvest, the pipe gate is opened to drain out the *Ulva* from the raceway ponds and *Ulva* is harvested in perforated baskets to allow the water to drain through. The raceway ponds (are) immediately reseeded with 500 kg of the *Ulva*”¹⁴⁵.

Stocking density in the paddle raceways at Buffeljags between 1 – 2 kg *Ulva* per m² of the pond surface area, which equates to a total biomass of roughly 1 – 1.5 tonnes of *Ulva* per raceway.

Figure 35. Manual harvesting of *Ulva lacinulata* at Buffeljags Abalone.

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4. HEALTH

The DFFE has developed a National Aquatic Animal Health Strategic Framework (hereafter referred to as the Framework) in South Africa to provide overarching strategic guidance for the management, control and regulation of aquatic animal health, welfare, and disease management in South Africa to facilitate export of abalone (and other aquacultured products) to international markets¹⁴⁶ (DAFF, 2013). Abalone cultivated in South Africa are mostly exported to Asian countries, primarily China, with a smaller percentage going to Taiwan, Singapore, and Malaysia. The World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH) publishes two international standards —the ‘Aquatic Animal Health Code’ and ‘Manual of Diagnostic Tests for Aquatic Animals’ — that forms the basis of the Framework. **The South African legislation and regulations relevant to aquatic animal health include:**

- The Fertilizers, Farm Feeds, Agricultural Remedies and Stock Remedies Act, 1947 (Act No 36 of 1947). This Act aims to “To provide for the appointment of a Registrar of Fertilizers, Farm Feeds and Agricultural Remedies, and for the registration of fertilizers, farm

¹⁴⁶ Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF), National Aquatic Animal Health Strategic Framework 2013.

feeds, agricultural remedies, stock remedies, sterilizing plants and pest control operators, and to regulate or prohibit the importation, sale, acquisition, disposal or use of fertilizers, farm feeds, agricultural remedies and stock remedies, and to provide for the designation of technical advisers and analysts, and to provide for matters incidental thereto."

- The Animals Protection Act, 1962 (Act No 71 of 1962) and Societies for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act, 1993 (Act No 169 of 1993). These Acts cover all aspects of cruelty to animals and the prevention thereof, including "being the owner of any animal, deliberately or negligently keeps such animal in a dirty or parasitic condition or allows it to become infested with external parasites or fails to render or procure veterinary or other medical treatment or attention which he or she is able to render or procure for any such animal in need of such treatment or attention, whether through disease, injury, delivery of young or any other cause, or fails to destroy or cause to be destroyed any such animal which is so seriously injured or diseased or in such a physical condition that to prolong its life would be cruel and would cause such animal unnecessary suffering."

- The Medicines and Related Substances Control Act, 1965 (Act No 101 of 1965) and Medicines and Related Substances Control Amendment Act, 1997 (Act No 90 of 1997). These Acts aim to "To provide for the registration of medicines intended for human and for animal use, and for the registration of medical devices, and for the establishment of a Medicines Control Council, for the control of medicines, scheduled substances and medical devices, for the control of manufacturers, wholesalers and distributors of medicines and medical devices, and for the control of persons who may compound and dispense medicines, and for matters incidental thereto."

- The Veterinary and Paraveterinary Professions Act, 1982 (Act No 19 of 1982). This Act aims "To provide for the establishment, powers and functions of the South African Veterinary Council, for the registration of persons practicing veterinary professions and paraveterinary professions, and for control over the practicing of veterinary professions and paraveterinary professions, and for matters connected therewith."

- The Animal Diseases Act, 1984 (Act No 35 of 1984) and Animal Disease Regulations. This Act and the regulations aim "To provide for the control of animal diseases and parasites, for measures to promote animal health, and for matters connected therewith."

- The Meat Safety Act, 2000 (Act No 40 of 2000). This Act aims “To provide for measures to promote meat safety and the safety of animal products; to establish and maintain essential national standards in respect of abattoirs; to regulate the importation and exportation of meat; to establish meat safety schemes; and to provide for matters connected herewith.”
- Other relevant legislation pertaining to animal health and welfare includes:
 - A list of all legislation which may impact on veterinarians can be found at the Faculty of Veterinary Science library (<http://www.ais.up.ac.za/vet/vetacts.htm>)
 - Animal disease legislation and controls can be found at <http://www.doa.agric.za> under Division of Veterinary Services.
 - More information is also available at the South African Veterinary Council site, <http://www.savc.co.za>, including the rules pertaining to the veterinary profession.

In addition to the above, protocols and standards have been developed specifically for aquaculture, addressing issues such as disease-free zones and stock movements, emergency response and preparedness, quarantine, listing of diseases, prevention of suffering, disposal of mortalities, decontamination, biosecurity, operation of harvesting vessels and processing facilities, and compliance and enforcement. The specific conditions are outlined in the various types of permits required to engage in marine aquaculture. A “right to engage in marine aquaculture” must be obtained from the DFFE when undertaking any commercial marine aquaculture activity, in terms of section 18 of the Marine Living Resources Act, 1998 (Act No. 18 of 1998) (MLRA). Permission to exercise such a “right” is granted by means of an annual permit, and rights holders must abide by the specific regulations outlined in the various permits governing, for example, hatcheries, grow-out, broodstock collection, transport, processing, and the import and export of marine aquaculture species and products. A “right to engage in marine aquaculture” is valid for 15 years, whereas marine aquaculture permits are renewable and valid for a period of 12 months.

More specifically to cultivate abalone, all farmers (Permit Holders) must comply with the active and passive components of the approved official surveillance program (Appendix A of the Health Management Procedures for South African Abalone produced for export).

5. BIOSECURITY

Biosecurity in aquaculture consists of practices that minimise the risk of introducing an infectious disease and spreading it to the animals at a facility and the risk that diseased animals or infectious agents will leave a facility and spread to other sites and to other susceptible species. These practices also reduce stress to the animals, thus making them less susceptible to disease agents¹⁴⁷.

Robust biosecurity systems are an essential pillar to healthy aquaculture production and a sustainable industry, protecting producers and emerging aquaculture sectors from the risks and threats of aquatic pathogens and diseases. The Animal Disease Act (Act 35 of 1984) in South Africa makes provision for the control of animal diseases and parasites and for measures to promote animal health¹⁴⁸. Aquaculture animals and products that are exported from South Africa require health certification. The latter has resulted in the development of animal health procedures to provide assurances of disease freedom and to demonstrate the maintenance of the animals' health status through the implementation of basic biosecurity conditions in accordance with WOA standards¹⁴⁹. Health management procedures for sea urchin and seaweed currently do not exist in South Africa. Conversely, specific procedures have been developed for abalone to comply with the basic biosecurity conditions prescribed by the WOA. These procedures stipulate that in order to export abalone permit holders must demonstrate freedom from the three diseases currently listed by the WOA for *Haliotis* species, namely, infections with abalone herpesvirus, *Perkinsus olseni* and *Xenohaliotis californiensis* — even though these diseases have never been detected in our local abalone species and *H. midae* has not been listed as a susceptible host species for any of these diseases¹⁴⁹.

Moreover, the health management procedures for South African abalone produced for export requires implementation of both passive and active surveillance programmes to ensure early detection of

¹⁴⁷ <https://thefishsite.com/articles/biosecurity-in-aquaculture-part-1-an-overview>.

¹⁴⁸ Government of South Africa (1984). – The Animal Diseases Act (Act 35 of 1984). National Gazette No. 9152 (3), 63 pp. Available at: www.nda.agric.za/vetweb/Legislation/Animal%20Diseases%20Act%20MAIN.htm.

¹⁴⁹ World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) (2018). – Aquatic Animal Health Code, 21st Ed. OIE, Paris, France. Available at: www.oie.int/standard-setting/aquatic-code/access-online/

disease introductions. Passive surveillance relies on the farm personnel, who are in contact with the animals daily, to recognise and report any suspected infections with WOAHA listed diseases, whereas targeted surveillance requires clinical inspection of the farmed population by a trained veterinarian. Biosecurity at the farm level is generally regarded as the responsibility of individual farms and in South Africa the Abalone Farmers Association of South Africa (AFASA), in conjunction with their private animal health service providers, have developed a basic biosecurity standard for farmed abalone¹⁵⁰.

Major goals of the biosecurity programme include the following key aspects:

- **Animal management:** obtaining healthy stocks and optimizing their health and immunity through good husbandry practices on farms.
- **Pathogen management:** preventing, reducing, or eliminating pathogens.
- **People management:** educating and managing staff and visitors.

Health surveillance is a critical component of a biosecurity programme, and the health and well-being of the animals must form part of the routine management tasks on the farm. These tasks must include, amongst others, daily inspection and monitoring when feeding animals and cleaning tanks as well as monthly internal health audits and comprehensive health checks by a trained veterinarian (once every 2 – 3 months) — to provide management with an early indication of potential health issues on the farm. **Daily/monthly animal health monitoring on the farm should include, amongst other things, observations of the following:**

- **Feed response:** Are the animals eating more or less?
- **Behaviour:** Any abnormal behaviour?
- **Breathing:** Struggling for air or congregating at top of baskets?
- **Appearance:** Visual marks, lesions, or sores?
- **Water quality:** O₂, pH, Temperature, Salinity, TAN, FAN
- **Morbidity or mortality**

¹⁵⁰ Christison, K.W. (2019) Building a sustainable aquaculture industry in South Africa: the role of biosecurity. Rev. Sci. Tech. Off. Int. Epiz. 38(2):589–600.

On-going or sudden increase in mortality should be reported to attending veterinarian immediately and to the competent authority in the country (normally required as part of standard permitting conditions). This is vital to ensure immediate response/management measures are implemented and that a proper diagnosis is made that will inform effective treatment and management interventions.

To minimise the risk of introducing and spreading an infectious disease agent at a facility and spreading it to other areas within the farm or to other sites/farms, biosecurity checkpoints are essential. Checkpoints typically include footbaths and hand sanitisers when entering and leaving the farm or different dedicated areas of the farm (e.g., hatchery, weaning and different sections of the grow-out platforms on the farm). Specific items of equipment are also dedicated to different areas to prevent spread of infectious disease agents and each section generally has dedicated workers. In the case of Buffeljags Abalone, the farm has been specifically designed to consist of modular units, with each abalone/sea urchin cluster linked to a single *Ulva* raceway regarded as an independent/epidemiological unit that can be isolated in the event of a disease outbreak without impacting production on the remainder of the farm. Biosecurity checkpoints require daily maintenance, and include, for example, replacement of disinfectant (e.g. Virkon-S) in footbaths, tidying of areas, sterilising equipment and uniform compliance. Daily records of all biosecurity and animal health procedures/monitoring must be maintained and reviewed on a regular basis by the biosecurity coordinator and farm management.

6. WELFARE

Animal health and welfare are interrelated, with animals in good health regarded as animals capable of performing physiological functions at normal levels and lacking disease or injury. Welfare, on the other hand, is the physical and mental state of an animal in relation to the conditions in which it lives and the capacity of the animal to cope with its environment. When responsible farming practices are implemented, such as those described in this document for the various species, then good health and welfare can be supported.

Animal welfare should be monitored daily, as described above, by assessing feed responses, animal behaviour and animal appearance.

A daily check list that keeps track of the animal inventory, system functionality, morbidity, mortality, feed response and habitus must be maintained to monitor animal welfare and provide early indication of suboptimal health/welfare. System functionality is a vital factor in land-based systems with partial recirculation, where water quality needs to be regularly monitored maintained within the optimal ranges for specific species and aeration needs to be continuously provided. Sea urchins are easily affected by poor water quality conditions and shock spawning, as a result of a system fault, can cause water quality to rapidly deteriorate and result in mortality. Therefore, it is vital that system functionality is assessed and maintained as needed as part of animal welfare assessments. A scoring system can be used to track feed responses, as animals not feeding is generally an indicator of poor animal welfare or an early indicator of stress and disease: (4) excellent, (3) good, (2) fair and (1) poor. Animal habitus can also be scored: (4) animals are behaving normally, (3) some animals with lesions/abnormalities or abnormal behaviour, (2) approximately half the animals display abnormal behaviour, (1) all animals displaying abnormal behaviour and (0) mass mortality. For sea urchins and abalone, abnormal behaviour would include animals not holding on to the baskets, all animals being at the bottom of a basket or being unresponsive.

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